

Stranded Renewable Energy Resources of Alaska

*A Preliminary Overview of Opportunities and Challenges
to Development*

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Executive Summary

Alaska is home to significant renewable energy resources. Geothermal, wind, tidal, wave, hydro and even solar and biomass resources have the theoretical potential to not only meet the majority of Alaska's in-state energy needs, but also provide tremendous economic and strategic opportunities for the State and the Nation. Despite the many opportunities for developing these resources, there are also significant barriers. Foremost among these challenges is the fact that many of Alaska's renewable energy resources are stranded.

Stranded renewables are those renewable energy resources located in remote, distant, or otherwise isolated areas "stranded" from integration into modern energy infrastructure and supply chains or utilization by local population and industry centers. Stranded renewables can be divided into two categories: (1) isolated or remote resources that are commercial- or export-scale in size (i.e. those energy resources that provide potential energy and economic value justifying remote development, and have large potential markets), and (2) resources "stranded" from utilization not by isolation or remote location, but due to such issues as economies of scale or "seasonality," such as abundant solar or hydro availability in the summer but not in the winter.

Typically, the primary barriers to developing stranded resources are technical, logistical, and economic barriers associated with the resource's remote location, including the cost of fully assessing the resource, developing the resource into usable energy, maintaining and operating a facility or technology in a remote location, and long distance transportation of the energy or product to demand centers. In Alaska, these barriers are amplified by the sheer size and diversity of the land, varying climates, extreme weather, and distance from global demand centers. Political and social barriers can also play a significant role when considering the development of stranded resources in Alaska. Land use restrictions, regulatory requirements, aesthetic concerns, environmental concerns, and other similar barriers could preclude the development of certain resources, or increase the overall cost of project development.

Developing Alaska's stranded renewable energy resources has been a popular topic of discussion recently, given concerns over declining oil production from the North Slope, the interest in diversifying and strengthening Alaska's economy, the rising cost in energy, and the energy security concerns of Alaska's communities. Energy security concern in particular has been an issue of late, including the vulnerability of Alaska's most remote villages to fluctuations in the price of diesel and the potential shortage of natural gas in Cook Inlet affecting Anchorage and other Railbelt communities.

The experience of other Arctic nations, notably Iceland and Norway, has contributed to this discussion given the many relevant similarities (availability and size of renewable energy resources, small populations, isolation, challenging logistics, and high energy costs) and the perceived success of these countries in developing and leveraging their renewable energy resources. In addition, changes in the Arctic climate have brought much attention to potential opportunities in stranded resource development. While winter navigation through the Arctic is still very limited, trends show sea ice extent in the Northern Hemisphere has been declining over the past five decades. Global climate models

predict a continuous decline in sea ice coverage throughout the 21st century¹. Shipping from Red Dog mine, for instance, has had record-early starts two of the last three years due to early ice melt².

Although stranded renewables and their potential have been frequently discussed in Alaska as of late, there has been little formal background work to inform the discussion. The purpose of this report is to outline the stranded renewable energy resources of Alaska and address the opportunities and challenges associated with developing these resources. It is important to note that given the breadth and complexity of the topic, this report is a simple overview serving as an introduction to the topic, providing background information and establishing a preliminary framework to inform this discussion, and a mechanism to identify next steps for further research, case studies, and assessments on the topic.

Alaska's Stranded Renewable Energy Resources

This report focuses on those stranded renewables that are export- or commercial- scale in size. The renewable energy resources considered to be relevant for this report include geothermal, wind, river (hydroelectric), and ocean (tidal and wave).

Geothermal

In 2008 the United States Geological Survey (USGS) estimated capacity of all known geothermal resources in Alaska at a mean of 677 MW over the next 30 years with a low range of 236 MW and a high of 1,359 MW³. Alaska's geothermal potential, however, is estimated from only a few existing wells and geophysical surveys of geothermal resources that are visible from the surface. Unidentified geothermal resources for Alaska are estimated to add an average of 1,788 MW, with a low of 537 MW and a high of 4,256 MW⁴.

Much of Alaska's potential geothermal energy capacity is significantly remote from major population centers or industry users. The Southwest region, which consists of the Alaska Peninsula and Aleutian Islands and is located on the "Ring of Fire," is one of the most remote regions and has the highest known geothermal capabilities in the state. At least 14 sites have been identified that potentially have high-temperature reservoirs (>302 °F) along the Aleutian arc, with a combined estimated potential to produce greater than 1,000 MW of electricity over a 30 year electrical production period⁵.

Given the high potential energy capacity of the resource and the ability of geothermal energy to provide base-load power generation for community and industrial applications in addition to direct usage, there is a great deal of interest in geothermal development opportunities. Of particular note, this interest is also influenced by the success of Iceland's geothermal industry. It is important to note that Iceland, a

¹ Arctic Council, "Arctic marine Shipping Assessment 2009 Report," <http://www.pame.is/amsa>, accessed 22 July 2011.

² DeMarban, A., "Summer Shipping begins for Red Dog Zinc," The Arctic Sounder, 29 June 2011, http://www.thearcticsounder.com/article/1126summer_shipping_begins_for_red_dog_zinc, accessed 22 July 2011.

³ Brookhart, T., et al., "Geothermal Energy Resources and Policies of the Western States," July 2009, http://www.blm.gov/pgdata/etc/medialib/blm/wo/MINERALS_REALTY_AND_RESOURCE_PROTECTION_/energy/geothermal_eis.Par.68458.File.dat/Geothermal_Resources_and_Policies_Western_US.pdf, accessed 18 Sept. 2011.

⁴ Brookhart, T., et al., "Geothermal Energy Resources and Policies of the Western States."

⁵ Motyka, R. J., et al., "Geothermal Resources of the Aleutian Arc," 1993, <http://www.dggs.dnr.state.ak.us/pubs/id/2314>, accessed 10 Sept 2011.

country often used for comparison to Alaska in terms of geothermal potential, is primarily a rift zone. Alaska is primarily a subduction zone, and could be an indicator for higher resource development costs.

Wind

Alaska has an abundance of potential wind resources, hosting the largest area of class 7 wind power in the United States⁶. Coastal areas such as Northern and Western Alaska, islands in the Gulf of Alaska and Bering Sea, the Aleutian Islands and mountainous areas throughout the state host the highest wind resources but also correspond to some of the remotest areas of Alaska. In addition, the offshore wind potential of Alaska, particularly along the Aleutian arc and off the islands in the Bering Sea, is tremendous.

Development of wind projects in Alaska has to date been limited primarily to small, localized projects in rural Alaskan communities along the western coast of Alaska. There are a few large-scale projects being developed as late, including the Eva Creek Project, Fire Island, and the Delta wind farm. The prospect of developing large-scale wind projects in remote locations, especially considering the intermittence of the resource and harsh climates of these areas, has been limited.

River

Hydroelectric power is the most abundantly developed renewable resource in the state and contributes 24% of the electricity consumed in Alaska⁷. The potential found throughout the state is enormous, and has widely been investigated for development. The Alaska State Legislature, for instance, passed a bill in April 2011 supporting the development of the Susitna hydroelectric project⁸. Susitna would be the largest hydroelectric project in the state, providing an estimated 600 MW of generation capacity for the Railbelt. Environmental concerns and development costs, however, are substantial barriers to the development of hydroelectric projects. Hydrokinetic power is another form of river energy currently being explored and developed in the state, although the technology is still in the pre-commercial phase and individual projects have little potential of being commercial- or export-scale in size.

Ocean

Ocean energy is one of the least developed renewable resources in Alaska, yet has some of the greatest energy potential. Total wave energy potential in Alaska is estimated to be 1,250 TWh/yr, over 50% of the total potential found in the US⁹. This translates to a vast untapped energy potential. Wave potential along the southern coast of Alaska and the Aleutian Islands, for example, is estimated to be almost 200 times the State's total annual energy needs.

⁶ Elliot, D.L. et al., "Wind Energy Resource Atlas of the United States," 1986, <http://rredc.nrel.gov/wind/pubs/atlas/>, accessed 8 Nov. 2011.

⁷ Alaska Energy Authority, Renewable Energy Alaska Project, "2009 Renewable Energy Atlas," <http://www.akenergyauthority.org/publications.html>, accessed 20 July 2011.

⁸ 27th Legislature, Bill History/Action for 27th Legislature, 12 April 2011, http://www.legis.state.ak.us/basis/get_bill.asp?bill=HB%20103, accessed 24 April 2011.

⁹ Bedard, R., "Prioritized Research, Development, Deployment and Demonstration (RDD&D) Needs: Marine and Other Hydrokinetic Renewable Energy," 2008, Electric Power Research Institute, http://oceanenergy.epri.com/attachments/ocean/reports/Final_MHK_Prioritized_RDD_Needs_Report_123108.pdf, accessed 12 Sept. 2011.

In addition to wave energy, Alaska is estimated to possess 90% of the tidal power in the U.S, or 109 TWh/yr¹⁰. The Cook Inlet, for example, has the second highest tidal range in North America and is of great interest for development of its tidal energy (though this would likely not be stranded because of its proximity to Alaska's primary population centers). Numerous sites in the Southeast, Cook Inlet and Aleutian Islands appear to have electrical generation potential of 25 MW or greater annually. The Aleutian Islands have a much greater potential with multiple sites estimated to produce between 75 MW and 220 MW annually¹¹.

Despite the vast potential in Alaska, the technology to capture and convert ocean energy is still pre-commercial, and much of Alaska's resource is in the remotest locations of the State. The immaturity of the technology has limited the development of resources globally. The additional element of remoteness in Alaska has to date made the discussion of developing Alaska's stranded ocean energy resource speculative at best.

Pathways to Development

The challenges and opportunities associated with developing Alaska's stranded renewables are assessed here via "pathways to development", that is, assessing those methods or mechanisms that allow for access to and development of stranded energy resources. These pathways consist of (1) the transportation of energy to market, (2) development and utilization of energy for localized industry, and (3) the development, demonstration, and deployment of technology relevant to accessing and developing Alaska's stranded renewables.

Transportation to Market

One pathway of developing a stranded resource is to overcome the resource's isolation by transporting the site-produced energy to market. Practically all methods of transporting energy over significant distances fall into two categories: electrical energy transmission or chemical energy transport. Electrical energy transmission is perhaps the more familiar and common of these two. It consists of converting the renewable energy resource into electrical energy, and transmitting that energy to market via electrical transmission lines. Electricity markets are connected by transmission systems. Accordingly, transmission has historically been at the center of discussion when considering the barriers and opportunities to developing stranded renewable energy resources. The cost of electrical transmission in Alaska is one of the most significant challenges to developing stranded renewable energy resources. Many factors such as permafrost and varying soil compositions, mountain ranges, rivers, limited access and extreme seasonal weather conditions can contribute to difficult engineering and construction challenges, and ultimately high costs.

One transmission opportunity of particular relevance to Alaska is high voltage, direct current (HVDC) transmission. HVDC transmission has many technical advantages as compared to traditional alternating

¹⁰ Bedard, R., "Prioritized Research, Development, Deployment and Demonstration (RDD&D) Needs: Marine and Other Hydrokinetic Renewable Energy," 2008, http://oceanenergy.epri.com/attachments/ocean/reports/Final_MHK_Prioritized_RDD_Needs_Report_123108.pdf, accessed 17 June 2011.

¹¹ Alaska Energy Authority, Renewable Energy Alaska Project, "2009 Renewable Energy Atlas," <http://www.akenergyauthority.org/publications.html>, accessed 20 July 2011.

current (AC) transmission. On overhead transmission lines, for instance, HVDC can use one or two wires, compared to the three or four wires needed for an AC line. This results in a direct material cost savings, and it can also significantly simplify the configuration and reduce the number of support structures, achieving additional savings. Long distance submarine or buried overland cables are also potentially less costly options with HVDC lines. Other advantages of HVDC transmission include: HVDC systems can have lower losses than comparable AC systems, HVDC systems can have smaller right-of-way requirements than AC systems, and HVDC provides an asynchronous transmission link, which can be advantageous in some power transmission grids.

HVDC infrastructure theoretically could allow for widespread access of stranded renewable energy resources throughout Alaska. The HVDC “super-grid”, a concept that has been proposed and analyzed for regions such as Europe¹², could allow for the inclusion of multiple intermittent renewable energy sources by averaging and smoothing the outputs of large numbers of geographically dispersed sources. HVDC transmission has often been discussed as a method of developing large-scale stranded renewable and non-renewable energy resources in Alaska, providing a potentially economical means of transporting produced power to population centers in the state or large, distant markets such as British Columbia and the Pacific Northwest.

There are substantial hurdles to consider, however, when considering HVDC for power transmission solutions to accessing stranded energy resources. Although promising in theory, multi-terminal HVDC grids and the networking of multiple HVDC sources into one grid have not been extensively demonstrated, creating a potentially high cost risk and reliability challenge for early adopters. While HVDC lines are usually more efficient than comparable AC lines the power conversion equipment used to convert AC to HVDC and back is generally less efficient and more expensive than AC transformers. This makes AC more cost effective for short interties, with HVDC more favorable for longer-distance transmission applications. The high cost of an HVDC power converter also forms an economic barrier that keeps energy resources or loads located along an HVDC transmission line from easily accessing the line. Perhaps most importantly in Alaska, HVDC power converters are only commercially available starting in the tens of MW of capacity, increasing to thousands of MWs for ‘world-class’ HVDC systems. This is simply too large to be of use for many of Alaska’s stranded renewable resources. The 5 MW_e (estimated) Pilgrim Hot Springs resource north of Nome is a good example. A 5 MW_e resource is too small to be economically developed using existing HVDC converter technology.

Chemical energy transport is most familiar in the context of fossil energy, primarily through the use of pipelines and marine tankers. Unlike fossil energy resources, which are harvested as a chemical energy resource, renewable energy must first be converted into a chemical energy form that is suitable for transportation. Only then can it be transported to energy markets via ship, pipeline, or other transportation methods. Additionally, with growing concerns over rising oil prices and increasing greenhouse gases, the production of alternative fuels has gained interest in order to reduce fossil fuel consumption, potentially stabilize energy prices, enhance energy security, and offset carbon and other

¹² Czisch, G., “Low Cost but Totally Renewable Electricity Supply for a Huge Supply Area, a European/Trans-European Example,” 2006, http://transnational-renewables.org/Gregor_Czisch/projekte/LowCostEuropEISup_revised_for_AKE_2006.pdf, accessed 15 Oct. 2011.

emissions. Some countries, especially in Asia and Europe, have begun to invest in alternative fuels such as hydrogen, ammonia, and dimethyl ether (DME) to move toward a sustainable, clean energy economy.

In Alaska, stranded renewable resources could potentially generate carbon free electricity to produce hydrogen through water electrolysis. Localized production of hydrogen can be used to make ammonia or methanol from stranded renewable resources such as wind, geothermal, hydroelectric or tidal power. As they are more mature technologies, wind and hydroelectric are more likely candidates for renewable hydrogen production at this time.

Because of hydrogen's low energy density, on-site use would be more economical than transporting it off-site. If produced from excess renewable energy, hydrogen could also be used to stabilize intermittent power systems in rural communities. Renewable to hydrogen technology is relatively new and still in development phase, though several projects, including geothermal-to-hydrogen in Hawaii, show significant promise¹³. Most of these demonstration projects are heavily subsidized through public and private investments, and are not economic given the current level of technological development and competing energy prices from more traditional resources.

Ammonia may be a technically easier option for distribution as it can be transported more easily in a liquid state, although it still suffers from a low energy density relative to other fuels such as diesel and gasoline. If used as a carrier, ammonia must be decomposed to extract the hydrogen, which requires a considerable amount of energy. Production costs are also significant, especially if made from hydrogen produced from electrolysis.

Ammonia was produced in Alaska until 2007 for fertilizer production using natural gas reformation. The plant, located in Nikiski on the Kenai Peninsula, shut down operations due to the inability to secure long-term access to a natural gas feedstock¹⁴. Alaska could attract industries, such as fertilizer production, with the incentive of low energy costs. Liquid ammonia can also be used directly as a fuel, although greater advancement in technology is needed at this time.

DME has high potential to be used as a substitute for diesel, which is used in abundance in the state. Because DME has no carbon-carbon bond, it is considered to be a clean burning fuel. A project of note that is being studied in Iceland is the development of a zero emissions DME production plant using renewable energy and carbon capture from flue gas. Production of DME could be beneficial to Alaska, however, at this time DME prices are not cost competitive with diesel or LPG. Production of DME is fairly expensive; there is currently limited production and capital costs to construct a plant are high. As fossil fuel prices rise, DME production should become more economical.

¹³ Rocheleau, R., Ewan, M., "Hawaii Hydrogen Power Park," Hawaii Natural Energy Institute, 2011 DOE Hydrogen and Fuel Cells Program Review, http://www.hydrogen.energy.gov/pdfs/review11/tv009_rocheleau_2011_p.pdf, May 2011.

¹⁴ Hermanek, P., "Agrium to mothball Nikiski facility," March 2008, http://peninsulaclarion.com/stories/031408/news_4013.shtml, accessed 30 Sept. 2011.

Place-Based Industry

An alternative approach to transporting produced energy to market is place-based industry, i.e., the development of stranded renewable energy resource for localized utilization. A specific form of industry, energy intensive industry (EII), is a primary candidate for place-based industry. EII is a general term for those industries that use large amounts of heat and/or other forms of energy to physically or chemically transform materials^{15,16}. These industries include, but are not limited to, the smelting of aluminum, mining, petroleum refinement, metal casting, the production of chemicals, steel, and glass, and forest products.

Smelting in particular is often discussed for application in Alaska. Smelting is the process of reducing mineral ores and concentrates to metal. Most methods involve heating the ore and concentrates with carbon to reduce the other ore compounds and, with additional refining, producing metal in a high state of purity ready for sale¹⁷. Smelting is an extremely energy intensive process. To produce a ton of aluminum, for example, it takes from 14.5 MWh to over 15 MWh¹⁸. In addition to high-energy demand, smelting operations require a large amount of infrastructure (the plant itself, access roads and shipping and dock facilities) and an optimized location. Proximity to global shipping routes, distance to raw material, distance to market, and ease of access, including the presence of a deep water port, are all critical elements to the overall feasibility of a smelting operation.

Preliminary metrics such as access to a large base-load renewable energy source, proximity to global shipping routes, presence of a deep water port, and supporting infrastructure requirements indicate that several sites throughout the Aleutian Islands, most notably Unalaska, could theoretically have the capacity to host smelting operations. Other EII such as mining and fish processing have theoretical applicability at various locations around the state, given suitable demand and the availability of a resource.

Another place-based industry of note with potential Alaskan application is the operation of data centers. Demand for data centers, driven by greater Internet use for business and entertainment has been exceeding supply, necessitating data center growth¹⁹. Energy use is the key concern of data centers. Depending on size, data centers can consume tens of kW for small applications to tens of MW for large facilities²⁰, with around half of the energy consumed by data centers used for cooling.

Technology companies operating data centers are investing heavily in renewable energy sources to increase corporate sustainability and reduce costs. In addition, operators are targeting innovative

¹⁵ United States Department of Energy, "Industrial Technologies Program: Energy Intensive Industry," 30 Nov. 2010, <http://www1.eere.energy.gov/industry/rd/industries.html>, accessed 3 Nov. 2011.

¹⁶ United States Department of Energy, "Industrial Technologies Program: Energy Intensive Industry," 30 Nov. 2010, <http://www1.eere.energy.gov/industry/rd/industries.html>, accessed 3 Nov. 2011.

¹⁷ Geevor Tin Mine Museum, "Smelting," 2009, <http://www.geevor.com/media/Smelting.pdf>, accessed on 20 Aug. 2011.

¹⁸ Burns, S., "Power Costs in the Production of Primary Aluminum," February 2009, <http://agmetminer.com/2009/02/26/power-costs-in-the-production-of-primary-aluminum/>, accessed on 31 Aug. 2011.

¹⁹ Miller, R., "Analysis: Demand Still Outpacing Supply," June 2010, <http://www.datacenterknowledge.com/archives/2010/06/28/analysts-demand-still-outpacing-supply/>, accessed 10 Sept. 2011.

²⁰ Silicon Valley Leadership Group, Data Center Energy Forecast, July 2008, <https://microsite.accenture.com/svlgreport/Pages/Home.aspx>, accessed 17 Sept. 2011.

methods to reduce energy consumed air conditioning loads. Cold-weather siting of data centers to incorporate ambient air cooling is increasingly becoming a key consideration in cutting costs.

Alaska possesses suitable stranded geothermal and wind resources sought by current data center operators and is a suitable cold-weather site for ambient cooling. Beyond the availability of renewable energy resources and cool ambient temperatures, however, location in relation to major data networks is a key consideration in the development of data centers. This is a particular hurdle for developing remote, place-based data centers in Alaska as no current infrastructure exists. Suitable network infrastructure has been proposed that could connect these relevant, remote areas of Alaska, such as Unalaska and sites along the west coast of Alaska, but substantial uncertainty still exists.

Overall, there are numerous hurdles to consider when discussing development of stranded renewable energy resources through place-based industry. Many of these hurdles deal with the remoteness of these potential sites and typical Alaskan challenges such as harsh climate operation. Others, including the high capital cost of such applications, speak more to the ability of developing a business model to move forward with these prospects. The following is an outline of some of these considerations:

- High construction costs — Remote locations, complex logistics, high material costs and the lack of an available local labor force can all contribute to expensive construction costs in the remote areas of Alaska. This is a substantial hurdle to overcome, especially when competing with countries like Iceland that have connective modern infrastructure throughout the country.
- High operations and maintenance costs – Similarly, operating and maintaining facilities in the remote areas of Alaska is expensive and challenging. These costs can often overshadow potential benefits of projects, particularly in long-term economic projections.
- Competitive cost of energy – Beyond the energy potential of the renewable energy resource and optimal location, the resulting cost of energy available to an EII is the ultimate driver for feasibility. Iceland’s cost of renewable energy is globally competitive, and a stringent benchmark for Alaska or other potential competitive markets.
- Competitive business environment — Iceland attracts foreign investment and EII in part through a competitive business environment, such as low corporate income tax rates. Iceland, for instance, offers a low corporate income tax of 20% on net income only²¹. Such policies would need to be assessed and potentially implemented in Alaska, similar to the tax credits for the film industry, to provide a competitive business environment.

Technology Development

A final pathway to developing Alaska’s stranded renewables is through technology development. Technology designed to harness and utilize renewable energy resources has been used for centuries and is always evolving in response to new technological breakthroughs. Due to the remoteness of Alaska’s renewable energy resources, traditional technology to generate and transmit power from renewable energy is being challenged. As interest in developing renewable energy in Alaska increases, new

²¹ OECD Tax Database, Taxation of corporate and capital income, http://www.oecd.org/document/60/0,2340,en_2649_34533_1942460_1_1_1_1,00.html#ccj, accessed 26 Feb. 2011.

technological advances could expand opportunities for the development of stranded renewable resource projects in rural regions of the state. An example of this is Alaska's Emerging Energy Technology Fund (EETF). Implemented by the Alaska legislature in 2010, this program seeks to "promote the expansion of energy sources available to Alaskans." Developing new technologies in the Alaskan context provides a unique opportunity to meet Alaskan energy needs, develop energy resources, and create global expertise.

There is much activity globally in pursuing next generation technologies with relevance to Alaska, such as floating offshore wind turbines, wave energy conversion devices, and tidal hydrokinetic generation technology. In addition, transmission and distribution technologies, control systems, and energy storage devices are all the focus of development, and could be relevant to developing stranded renewables in Alaska.

Conclusions and Recommendations

During this initial investigation of stranded renewables in Alaska, it became apparent that the breadth and depth of detailed technical and economic information required to fully inform this discussion is substantial. As a first step, we have focused this report on introducing the tremendous renewable energy resources in Alaska, the success of countries like Iceland and Norway in developing their perceived similar resources, and some of the relevant methods and technologies that could have theoretical application in Alaska. The drivers and particulars are, of course, much more complicated.

Preliminary Findings

From a general level, it is clear from the experience of countries like Norway and Iceland that developing commercial- and export-scale renewable energy resources requires strong supportive policy and strategic government planning. To date, Alaska has neither outside of oil and gas policy specifically targeting state revenue generation. Such policy and planning efforts are essential for Alaska to utilize its stranded renewable resources to meet domestic energy needs and seek new opportunities for economic growth and diversification.

Fully understanding Alaska's potential for developing stranded renewable energy is limited in part due to a lack of comprehensive resource assessments. For example, there is currently limited information related to state-wide and site-specific geothermal resource potential or wave and tidal potential. This hampers strategic energy planning, business planning, and project development. As a comparison, the State currently takes an active role in wind resource assessments for feasibility and planning efforts, a vital step to developing the many recent wind projects over the past several years. The State could translate these efforts to resources such as geothermal and ocean energy, although it is true that such efforts are much more expensive than wind resource assessments. Specific to ocean energy, the State has begun such efforts by partnering with NOAA and conducting a comprehensive resource assessment of Cook Inlet.

In terms of technological development, HVDC technology has significant potential for use in Alaska, theoretically allowing for access, integration, distribution, and even export of stranded renewable energy resources. Countries like Norway are widely utilizing this form of transmission and pioneering its

use for exporting renewable energy, and have had much economic success in doing so. These opportunities for Alaska, however, have had little technical and economic analysis, particularly in the context of state-wide strategic infrastructure planning. The "Alaska Backbone" concept, for instance, is an exciting proposal on paper, but has had little comparative analysis to current proposed infrastructure projects like a natural gas pipeline, let alone an independent feasibility analysis. In addition, much of the innovative HVDC technology that are critical to these opportunities for Alaska, such as multi-terminal HVDC grids and small-scale HVDC converters, are in the pre-commercial stage and have had limited demonstration and deployment.

Place-based industry, smelting and data centers in particular, theoretically have great potential in the State given Alaska's position relative to global transportation lanes, the availability of commercial-scale renewable resources, and other advantages such as cool ambient temperatures and geographic location. It is important to note, however, that the economic assessment of these opportunities has not been investigated in detail enough to truly justify recommendation. These efforts in particular would need to be linked to a strong supportive State policy, similar to the high level of government support and incentives offered by countries like Iceland. Minor advantages in the overall cost of electricity have dramatic ramifications for the bottom line of such operations. Ultimately, the delivered cost of electricity for any large operation would need to be competitive with prices offered by other Arctic nations possessing lower barriers, real or perceived, associated with distance from major support centers.

Technology development is a critical activity to both accessing and utilizing Alaska's stranded renewable energy resources. With the enactment of the Emerging Energy Technology Fund (AS 42.45.375) in 2011, the State has recognized this role, and the need for innovation in expanding our available energy solutions. There is still need, however, to integrate this program and others into an overall strategic energy plan for the State, ensuring that promising solutions have the opportunity to be implemented in the future, and that Alaskan businesses can be competitive in emerging energy markets.

Next Steps

The goal of this paper was to introduce the topic of stranded renewables in Alaska and outline a framework by which to formally consider the topic. It is clear that there is much more research needed to further inform a serious discussion on the development potential of Alaska's stranded energy resources. As a next step, ACEP and NREL propose conducting a more comprehensive assessment that better delineates that opportunities and challenges associated with development of stranded energy resources. The following list summarized some opportunities for a more detailed analysis, as identified by this paper, and mentions potential key partner organizations in addition to the authors of this report:

- **Policy Assessment:** It is recommend completing a detailed policy review of analogous countries like Iceland, Norway, and Canada specifically focused on the development and utilization of stranded renewables and relevant lessons learned for Alaska, given the State's political framework and current economic climate. Organizations such as the Institute of Social and Economic Research (ISER), Renewable Energy Alaska Project (REAP) and the Institute of the North would be key partners in such an effort.

- Shipping and the Arctic: Given the current decrease in sea ice in the Arctic, better assessing the foreseen challenges and opportunities associated with accessing and developing Alaska's stranded renewable energy resources should be a priority at both the State and Federal level. Organizations such as the Institute of the North and the Arctic Counsel, and forums such as the Arctic Imperative are important organizations to engage, in coordination with a broader Arctic community.
- Alternative Fuels: The issues surrounding the production of alternative fuels is very complex, as it touches on many interlinking issues including strategic energy and infrastructure planning, economic development, international markets, technology implementation, and economics. It is also a key aspect to understanding the economics and opportunity of stranded renewable development. It is recommend conducting a more comprehensive investigation of the opportunities and challenges specific to alternative fuel production in comparison to other proposed options relevant to stranded renewables. In addition to NREL, ISER, the Alaska Energy Authority, the Arctic Energy Office, other State, Federal, and University entities, and key private sector analysts and industry members would be vital to sufficiently addressing such a complex component to this topic.
- Economic Assessment: To this point, the challenges and opportunities of developing stranded renewables have not been addressed through the lens of a comprehensive economic assessment. This aspect is critical to furthering the discussion, whether related to policy development or specific opportunities such as HVDC transmission. Potential partners range from State and Federal economic ,regulatory, and resource entities, to regional government, economic, and development entities to private sector consulting and project firms.
- Case Studies: Specific and detailed case studies on relevant theoretical projects are needed to better shape and inform future discussion on this topic. Examples include a smelting operation or data center on Unalaska, or investigating the development of HVDC infrastructure for utilization of North Slope natural gas, rural transmission, or access to a discrete stranded resource. Potential partners are wide-ranging depending on the resource, project, and focus of the case study.
- HVDC: In order to further assess the opportunities for HVDC in Alaska, close monitoring of current activities and lessons learned internationally needs to occur. In Canada, for instance, the government of Manitoba is seeking to connect its most remote communities through innovative transmission methods. Small-scale HVDC transmission is of particular interest, and if implemented, could provide a source of critical lessons learned for Alaska. Monitoring the development of relevant HVDC infrastructure, and perhaps pursuing the demonstration of this technology here in Alaska, are also important activities. Finally, detailed economic assessments of proposed and potential HVDC solutions is critical, as little analysis has been formally completed, particularly in comparison with other currently proposed energy infrastructure solutions for the State. Key partners include AEA, ISER, the Department of Labor, the Alaska Power Association and its member utilities, and the Cooperative Research Network.

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Introduction

From the vast oil and natural gas resources on the North Slope, to the estimated potential of offshore fields in the Chukchi Sea and the Arctic National Wildlife Refuge, to the large coal deposits of the Interior, the focus of both the State and the Nation is on the current production and future potential of Alaskan fossil energy resources. Alaska, however, is also home to significant renewable energy resources. Geothermal, wind, tidal, wave, hydro and even solar and biomass resources have the theoretical potential to not only meet the majority of Alaska's in-state energy needs, but also provide tremendous economic and strategic opportunities for the State and the Nation. Despite the many opportunities for developing these resources, there are also significant barriers. Foremost among these challenges is the fact that many of Alaska's renewable energy resources are stranded.

Stranded renewables, for the purpose of this report, are those renewable energy resources located in remote, distant, or otherwise isolated areas "stranded" from integration into modern energy infrastructure and supply chains or utilization by local population and industry centers.

Stranded renewables and their potential have been frequently discussed in Alaska as of late, but with little formal background work to inform the discussion. The purpose of this report is to outline the stranded renewable energy resources of Alaska and address the opportunities and challenges associated with developing these resources. It is important to note that given the breadth and complexity of the topic, this report is a simple overview serving as an introduction to the topic, providing background information and establishing a preliminary framework to inform this discussion, and a mechanism to identify next steps for further research, case studies, and assessments on the topic.

This report is organized by the following sections:

Pathways to Developing Stranded Renewables in Alaska, divided into three sections, is a discussion of the critical pathways that could facilitate the development of Alaska's stranded renewables. The first section, *Transportation to Market*, discusses development of stranded renewables through transporting produced energy to market for off-site utilization. The second section, *Place-Based Industry*, discusses development of stranded renewable energy resources for on-site utilization. The final section, *Technology*, discusses relevant energy technologies that are pre-commercial or early in commercialization but, if further developed and demonstrated, could significantly impact the ability to economically develop Alaska's stranded renewable resources.

Conclusions and Recommendations is the synthesis of conclusions from the report, and includes general and specific recommendations of the authors to both further the understanding of this topic and investigate the opportunities identified throughout the report. In addition, two appendices have been attached to this report. **Appendix A: Overview of Stranded Renewables in Alaska** is a summary of Alaska's stranded renewables and a discussion of relevant considerations for framing potential pathways to development. **Appendix B: Shipping in the Arctic** examines the infrastructure, routes, and developing opportunities (such as the opening of the Northwest Passage) in Arctic shipping that could impact the development of Alaska's stranded renewables.

Pathways to Developing Stranded Renewables in Alaska

Stranded renewables are those renewable energy resources that are remote, distant, or otherwise located in isolated areas “stranded” from integration into modern energy infrastructure and supply chains. For the purposes of this report, Alaska’s stranded renewable resources include geothermal, wind, river (hydroelectric), and ocean (tidal and wave). This report focuses on resources that are potentially commercial or export scale in size, i.e., those energy resources that provide potential energy and economic value to justify remote development, and have large potential markets. Typically, the primary barriers to developing such resources are technical, logistical, and economic barriers associated with the resource’s remote location, including the cost of fully assessing the resource, developing the resource into usable energy, maintaining and operating a facility or technology in a remote location, and long distance transportation of the energy or product to demand centers. Similarly, though natural gas is not a renewable resource, Alaska’s massive gas deposits on the North Slope are currently stranded because of the costs and risks associated with transporting the gas to distant markets.

In Alaska, these barriers are amplified by the sheer size and diversity of the land, varying climates, extreme weather, and distance from global demand centers. Alaska covers nearly 586,000 square miles and is sparsely populated outside of its few major urban centers. There are over 180 small remote Alaskan communities that are on individual isolated electric grids powered mostly by small diesel generators (decentralized generation). Even Alaska’s largest electrical grid, the Railbelt, is small by 48 standards, especially when considering the large geographic expanse it covers. With an estimated peak load of 870 MW¹, the entire Railbelt grid is smaller than the typical generating capacity of a single Lower 48 power plant. The State’s resource potential, in spite of these barriers, is tremendous, ranging from geothermal energy in the Aleutians to wind potential in western Alaska to wave and tidal resources in southeast Alaska (see *Appendix A: Overview of Stranded Renewables in Alaska* for more information).

A separate but also significant means by which renewables are stranded is political barriers. In essence, political barriers are decisions made by society that preclude development of certain resources. Perhaps the most prominent Alaska example of a political barrier to the development of a fossil energy resource is the Federal prohibition on oil and gas exploration and development within Alaska’s Arctic National Wildlife Refuge.

The challenges and opportunities associated with developing Alaska’s stranded renewables are assessed here via pathways of development, that is, those methods or technologies that allow for access to and development of stranded energy resources. These pathways, for the purpose of this report, consist of the transportation of energy to market (*Transportation to Market*), development and utilization of energy for localized industry (*Place-based Industry*), and the development, demonstration, and deployment of technology relevant to accessing and developing Alaska’s stranded renewables (*Technology*).

¹Black and Veatch, Alaska Railbelt Regional Integrated Resource Plan (RIRP) Study, Feb. 2010.

It is important to note that although this report focuses on resources that are commercial- or export-scale in size, there are other classes of renewable energy resources “stranded” from utilization not by isolation or remote location, but due to such issues as economies of scale or “seasonality,” such as abundant solar or hydro availability in the summer but not in the winter. The pathways to developing such resources, although sometimes similar to those outlined below, can differ in approach. The pathways explored below are specific to those resources of commercial- or export-scale size, and stranded in part due to isolation and remote location.

Transportation to Market

A stranded renewable, in the most generalized definition, is a renewable energy resource that is isolated from an energy market. One pathway of developing a stranded resource is to overcome the resource’s isolation by transporting the site-produced energy to market. Practically all methods of transporting energy over significant distances fall into two categories: electrical energy transmission or chemical energy transport. In both cases the stranded renewable energy is captured, converted, and transported offsite for utilization

Electrical energy transmission is perhaps the more familiar and common of these two. It consists of converting the renewable energy resource into electrical energy, and transmitting that energy to market via electrical transmission lines. Chemical energy transport is most familiar in the context of fossil energy, as oil pipelines and marine tankers. Unlike fossil energy resources, which are harvested as a chemical energy resource, renewable energy must first be converted into a chemical energy form that is suitable for transportation. Only then can it be transported to energy markets via ship, pipeline, or other transportation methods. Promising conversion and transport schemes for Alaska are briefly introduced in this section.

Transmission

Electricity markets are connected by transmission systems. Accordingly, transmission has historically been at the center of discussion when considering the barriers and opportunities to developing stranded renewable energy resources. The cost of electrical transmission in Alaska is one of the most significant challenges to developing stranded renewable energy resources. Many factors such as permafrost and varying soil compositions, mountain ranges, rivers, limited access and extreme seasonal weather conditions can contribute to difficult engineering and construction challenges, and ultimately high costs. Transmission lines can range from \$100,000/mile to \$2,000,000/mile or more depending on the voltage, wire size, terrain, icing conditions, accessibility, need for accompanying roads, and structure type². The following projects highlight both cost and challenge:

- Pilgrim Hot Springs (see *Appendix A*) is located approximately 60 miles north of Nome by road. This is the largest identified geothermal resource on mainland Alaska and could likely be developed to meet all or most of Nome’s electric load. Two estimates for the construction of a transmission line from a proposed 5 MW power plant at Pilgrim Hot Springs to Nome were outlined in a preliminary feasibility study prepared for the Alaska Energy Authority. Assuming

² AEA, ACEP, “Alaska Energy, A first step toward energy independence,” Jan. 2009.

the use of a single pole structure and winter construction for tundra protection, the first estimate quoted a range between \$500,000 and \$750,000 per mile for a total cost of \$30 to \$40 million. The second estimate ranged from \$164,000 to \$450,000 per mile, although, the cost per mile was doubled in the feasibility study to accommodate for the “Alaska Factor”. Total cost for the second estimate was between \$20 and \$54 million³. This is significantly higher than the estimated cost to build the power plant itself, and may make the project uneconomical.

- The proposed 50-100 MW Mount Spurr geothermal power plant (see *Appendix A*) is located approximately 75 miles from Anchorage. Between 35 to 45 miles of new transmission line is needed to connect Mount Spurr to the existing Railbelt transmission grid at the Beluga Power Plant near Tyonek. An Alaskan engineering consulting firm estimated that the proposed transmission line would cost between \$300,000 and \$600,000 per mile for a total cost of \$10 to \$27 million⁴. Ormat, the company proposing to develop Mount Spurr, estimates the total cost for the transmission line to be much higher, at around \$70 million, or approximately \$1.5 to \$2 million per mile⁵.

In addition to construction and installation challenges, political barriers such as permitting and regulatory requirements are substantial hurdles for many transmission projects. For example, in parts of the Tongass National Forest in Southeast Alaska the federal ‘Roadless Rule’ forbids the construction of new roads, forcing transmission projects to utilize helicopters for installation in many areas. In other parts of the state, in particular the North Slope and the Yukon-Kuskokwim Deltas, concerns about the effects of transmission lines on migratory birds can lead to costly environmental studies and mitigation or avoidance measures that increase project costs. More generally, land use restrictions, aesthetic concerns, environmental concerns, and similar political barriers preclude otherwise technically or economically favorable transmission routes and lead to less economical projects or stranded renewable resources. Many of these political barriers are founded in sound science and sensible public policy, yet others are nation-wide policies that fail to recognize the unique realities of rural Alaska, and the profound economic challenges that confront many rural Alaska communities.

High Voltage Direct Current (HVDC)

One transmission opportunity of particular relevance to Alaska is high voltage, direct current (HVDC) transmission. HVDC transmission has been utilized commercially since the 1950’s, beginning with projects in Russia and Sweden, and is most often used for bulk transmission of power over long distances. The following table summarizes several relevant HVDC projects around the world:

³ Dilley, L.M., “Preliminary Feasibility Study Pilgrim Hot Spring,” April 2007.

⁴ Dilley, L.M, “Infrastructure Development for a Geothermal Field at Mount Spurr, Alaska.”

⁵ Bradner, T., “Southcentral utilities wrestle with pricey power options,” April 2011, http://www.alaskajournal.com/stories/042111/oil_suwpp.shtml, accessed on 28 Oct. 2011.

System/Project	Commissioned (Year)	Power Rating (MW)	DC Voltage (kV)	Line Length (miles)
Gotland III <i>Sweden</i>	1987	260	±150	64
Gotland HVDC Light <i>Sweden</i>	1999	50	±60	44
Pacific Intertie Expansion <i>Washington to California, USA</i>	1989	3,100	±500	846
Cahora-Bassa <i>Mozambique to Johannesburg, South Africa</i>	1979	1,920	±533	882
Inga-Shaba <i>Democratic Republic of Congo</i>	1983	560	±500	1,056
Quebec-New England <i>North America</i>	1992	2,250	±450	932
Xiangjiaba – Shanghai <i>China</i>	2010	6,400	±800	804

Table 1: Major HVDC Projects⁶

HVDC transmission has many technical advantages as compared to traditional alternating current (AC) transmission. Of greatest relevance to Alaska’s stranded renewables, HVDC offers a lower-cost alternative to AC transmission in many applications. HVDC transmission can achieve lower costs than AC transmission in several different ways. On overhead transmission lines, HVDC can use one or two wires, compared to the three or four wires needed for an AC line. This results in a direct material cost savings, and it can also significantly simplify the configuration and reduce the number of support structures, achieving additional savings. Long distance submarine or buried overland cables are also potentially less costly options with HVDC lines. AC cannot always use long distance submarine or buried cables because of the way that AC power reacts to the capacitance of cables. Currently the longest submarine HVDC cable in the world is NorNed, spanning a distance of 360 miles across the Baltic Sea, connecting the Norwegian and Netherland power grids. NorNed, which has been operational since 2008, has a capacity of 700 MW. The cost to install HVDC submarine cables is still expensive, ranging from \$1.4 million/mile to nearly \$9 million/mile, but given a large enough project, can be economical⁷. The NorNed project was completed for a cost of \$940 million and was estimated to have a profit of \$100 million annually; however, within the first two months NorNed saw profits of \$78 million, far exceeding original predictions⁸.

Other advantages of HVDC transmission include: HVDC systems can have lower losses than comparable AC systems, HVDC systems can have smaller right-of-way requirements than AC systems, and HVDC provides an asynchronous transmission link, which can be advantageous in some power transmission grids.

⁶ Sources used for Table 1: HVDC Projects Listing, Working Group on HVDC and FACTS Bibliography and Records, Nov. 2006, <http://www.ece.uidaho.edu/hvdcfacts/>, accessed 10 Nov. 2011.

⁷ Tierney, S.F., et al., “Strategic Options for Investment in Transmission in Support of Offshore Wind Development in Massachusetts,” Jan. 2010.

⁸ Parail, V., “Properties of Electricity Prices and the Drivers of Interconnector Revenue,” Nov. 2010.

Of course, HVDC is not a panacea for power transmission. While HVDC lines are usually more efficient than comparable AC lines the power conversion equipment used to convert AC to HVDC and back is generally less efficient and more expensive than AC transformers. This makes AC more cost effective for short interties, with HVDC more favorable for longer-distance transmission applications. The high cost of an HVDC power converter also forms an economic barrier that keeps energy resources or loads located along an HVDC transmission line from easily accessing the line. Perhaps most importantly in Alaska, HVDC power converters are only commercially available starting in the 10s of MW of capacity, increasing to 1,000s of MWs for ‘world-class’ HVDC systems. This is simply too large to be of use for many of Alaska’s stranded renewable resources. The 5 MW Pilgrim Hot Springs resource north of Nome is a good example. A 5 MW resource is far too small to be economically developed using existing HVDC converter technology.

HVDC for Export

HVDC transmission has often been discussed as a method of developing large-scale stranded renewable energy resources in Alaska, providing an economical means of transporting produced power to large, distant markets. One of the earliest references to HVDC use for an Alaska project was in 1954 when construction of a dam and large hydroelectric project was proposed on the Yukon River near Rampart. The project would have been one of the largest hydropower projects in the world, with a dam height of 530 feet and span of 4,700 feet across, creating a reservoir larger than Lake Erie. Electrical generation from the Rampart Dam would have been between 3.5 and 5 GW of instantaneous power. As energy produced from the Rampart Dam project would have been too great for an Alaskan market, studies at the time suggested that the project could be used to attract energy intensive industries, such as aluminum smelters, as well as provide export power to southern British Columbia (BC) or the Pacific Northwest (PNW)^{9,10}. Eventually the project was abandoned due to the uncertainty of attracting outside investment, the large size of the project in a small market, and serious environmental concerns¹¹.

Similar proposals to install HVDC transmission lines from other parts of Alaska to BC and the PNW for energy export are numerous. In 1982 the U.S. Department of Energy, Alaska Power Administration, concluded a follow-up study from a 1972 assessment of an 8,000 MW HVDC transmission line between the North Slope, BC, and PNW from coal and gas-fired generation¹². Although the study found that further analysis of the project was not warranted and the North Slope transmission line was not approved for construction, the idea of exporting Alaskan generated energy, fossil or renewable, is still a plausible concept. The following is a brief summary of current or recent project proposals:

- In 2007 a feasibility study was conducted on exporting Southeast Alaska hydroelectric power to BC and PNW. The study concluded that there is a possible market for the exportation of energy, especially as energy consumption is expected to grow substantially. No “fatal flaws” in the

⁹ U.S. Department of Defense, Department of the Army, Army Corps of Engineers. The Market For Rampart Power- Yukon River, Alaska (Washington D.C.: U.S. Government Printing Office, April 1962).

¹⁰ U.S. Department of the Interior, Bureau of Reclamation. Alaska Natural Resources and the Rampart Project (Washington D.C.: U.S. Government Printing Office, June 1967).

¹¹ Gunter Schramm, The Role Of Low-Cost Power In Economic Development (New York: Arno Press, 1979).

¹² NANA Pacific, “Distributing Alaska’s Power: A technical and policy review of electric transmission in Alaska,” Dec. 2008.

development of the AK-BC intertie were found; however, constructing a project across international borders requires coordination and further consultation with Canada. If the project were realized, a transmission line from hydroelectric generation in the Southeast would be connected to the BC transmission system. The AK-BC intertie would possibly promote the development of transmission infrastructure within Southeast Alaska as well¹³.

- The Tollhouse Energy Company, a privately owned Washington-based corporation, has several hydroelectric projects that have been completed in Alaska. The company has also proposed to connect the Western United States to Alaskan and Canadian hydroelectric and wind energy resources via a 2,200 MW HVDC submarine line, called the Green Pacific Highway project, in an effort to reduce energy constraints. Progress of the Green Pacific Highway project is not known at this time, although costs have been estimated at \$4.54 billion over a 9 year period¹⁴.
- A study proposing to build a 10 GW gas turbine power plant on Alaska's North Slope and transmit electricity 2,300 miles over an 800 kV underground HVDC transmission line to Calgary, Alberta, was completed in 2008¹⁵. The proposed transmission line would cost approximately \$5.6 billion, while total costs for the project were estimated to be \$18.1 billion. The study found that exporting electricity over an HVDC line would likely be more profitable than constructing a natural gas pipeline and associated infrastructure to export the gas to market.
- ABB Power Systems and Marsh Creek LLC have proposed two projects that would utilize North Slope gas to generate electricity for transmission and export: the 'Alaska Power Backbone' and 'Power Line South'.
 - 'Alaska Power Backbone' would consist of transmitting 1 GW of electricity 860 miles over a \pm 500 kV bipolar HVDC line, offloading in Fairbanks and Anchorage. At \$2.46 billion, the project is estimated to distribute power at 3.7 cents per kWh. A western HVDC transmission line to Kotzebue was also proposed as well as a submarine HVDC line from Anchorage to the western U.S. coast rather than through Canada¹⁶.
 - 'Power Line South', the second proposal, would follow the same basic format as Alaska Power Backbone but at higher electrical production with the plan to export excess energy to Canada and the Lower 48. The gas fueled power plant would produce 6,400 MW of electricity, thus transmitting 6.4 GW over a \pm 800 kV HVDC line. Fairbanks and Anchorage would receive the same amount of electricity as in the Alaska Power Backbone project and the surplus would be exported south on an HVDC transmission line from Fairbanks. Capital cost for the Power Line South project is estimated to be \$10.89 billion and distribute electricity at 2.6 cents per kWh¹⁷.

Assessing Alaska's Opportunities

Although many of these projects target fossil fuel generation, in particular North Slope natural gas, such HVDC infrastructure could allow for widespread access of stranded renewable energy resources

¹³ Hatch Acres, "AK-BC Intertie Feasibility Study SE Alaska," Sept. 2007.

¹⁴ Tollhouse Energy Company, "Green Pacific Highway," January 2009, www.tollhouseenergy.com/Projects.html, accessed 25 Sept. 2011.

¹⁵ Freitas, S., "Alaska Electric Line," 2008.

¹⁶ Anderson, Jr., N., "State of Alaska Energy Policy and Strategy Recommendations," Feb. 2007.

¹⁷ Jacobsen, R. A., et al., "Gas to Wires – Electrical Power from the North Slope," July 2011.

throughout Alaska. The HVDC “super-grid”, a concept that has been proposed and analyzed for regions such as Europe¹⁸, could allow for the inclusion of multiple intermittent renewable energy sources by averaging and smoothing the outputs of large numbers of geographically dispersed sources. Challenges remain, however. Although promising in theory, multi-terminal HVDC grids and the networking of multiple HVDC sources into one grid have not been extensively demonstrated, creating a potentially high cost risk and reliability challenge for early adopters.

A primary barrier to utilizing HVDC for stranded renewables, despite the potential capital and construction cost savings of the HVDC transmission system, has been the tremendous cost of the DC conversion equipment when considered for medium- and small-scale applications. For medium-scale needs, technology such as ABB’s HVDC Lite may offer opportunities to economically access stranded resources. In addition, active development is currently under way for small-scale HVDC transmission systems for remote Alaska applications¹⁹. Polarconsult Alaska, Inc., in partnership with Princeton Power Systems, is in the final stages of developing a 1 MW AC to HVDC converter system that aims to eventually be fully reliable and cost competitive²⁰. This converter technology, undergoing final testing in December 2011, is estimated to cost under \$500,000 per MW, and when compared to traditional AC transmission systems, shows some promise in the long-term but is currently in the development stage:

- In a study prepared for the Denali Commission, Polarconsult compared the costs of a 25-mile overhead AC intertie to (1) their HVDC innovative ‘Long-Span Tall-Pole’ single-wire earth return (SWER, see description below) intertie and (2) a conventionally built two-wire HVDC intertie. The initial results showed that the HVDC innovative SWER intertie was nearly \$3 million less to install compared to the AC intertie. The conventional two-wire HVDC intertie was more comparable in cost, saving little more than \$900,000 over the AC intertie. The cost for a typical overhead AC line was found to be less expensive over a short distance than HVDC due to the fixed cost of the power converters that are required on each end of the HVDC transmission line. However, after the transmission lines reached a distance longer than 9 to 16 miles, depending on whether it is a single or double line, the projected cost of both HVDC interties became progressively less, resulting in a lower per-mile cost²¹.

Another area of opportunity is in reducing costs of materials and construction methods used for transmission infrastructure. The use of fiberglass poles, nesting poles, long spans, and innovative foundations all have the potential of reducing the installed cost of transmission lines. One innovation that is used extensively internationally for low-cost, small-scale rural power transmission and that has previously been investigated for cost reduction in Alaska is AC SWER systems.

¹⁸ Czisch, G., “Low Cost but Totally Renewable Electricity Supply for a Huge Supply Area, a European/Trans-European Example,” 2006, http://transnational-renewables.org/Gregor_Czisch/projekte/LowCostEuropEISup_revised_for_AKE_2006.pdf, accessed 15 Oct. 2011.

¹⁹ Polarconsult Alaska, Inc., “HVDC Transmission System For Remote Alaska Applications Phase I: Preliminary Design and Feasibility Analysis,” Aug. 2009.

²⁰ This project is funded through a grant from the Denali Commission. Phase 1 was managed by the Alaska Village Electric Cooperative, while Phase 2 was managed by the Alaska Center for Energy and Power, the author of this report.

²¹ Polarconsult Alaska, Inc., “HVDC Transmission System For Remote Alaska Applications Phase I: Preliminary Design and Feasibility Analysis,” Aug. 2009.

- In 1980, two experimental single phase AC SWER systems were installed in western rural Alaska. SWER works by using either an overhead or submarine wire for the high-voltage portion of a transmission circuit, and the earth as a return pathway to complete the circuit instead of a second metallic conductor. Using a SWER system in remote regions could decrease the cost of installing the transmission line by reducing the amount of infrastructure needed.
 - One of the experimental AC SWER transmission lines was constructed between Bethel and Napakiak, stretching 8.5 miles. The total cost was \$280,000, or approximately \$33,000 per mile in 1980 dollars. Over the years, however, the line has deteriorated causing line loss, poor reliability and more expensive energy costs. As a result, this line was upgraded to a 10.5 mile long standard three-phase line at a cost of about \$3.1 million in 2010, or approximately \$298,000 per mile²².
 - The second 10.5-mile experimental AC SWER line was built in 1980 between Shungnak and Kobuk. It was also rebuilt in 1991 as a 15 kV, three-phase line at a cost of \$1,350,000²³.

SWER circuits are also used successfully internationally for large and small-scale HVDC systems. Many HVDC projects have been built in phases, with the first phase consisting of a single pole operating as a SWER circuit, and the second phase upgrading this SWER system to a bipolar system once the load grows enough to justify the increased system cost. Small-scale HVDC SWER circuits are currently being investigated in the Polarconsult project, listed above.

Alternative Fuel Production

Electricity is only one form of an energy product that can be commoditized and transported to market. Another option is converting a renewable energy resource to alternative fuels, typically in liquid or gaseous form, and then transporting these fuels to market via pipeline, rail, or ship. With growing concerns over rising oil prices and increasing greenhouse gases, the production of alternative fuels has gained interest in order to reduce fossil fuel consumption, potentially stabilize energy prices, enhance energy security, and offset carbon and other harmful emissions. Some countries, especially in Asia and Europe, have begun to invest in alternative fuels such as hydrogen, ammonia, and dimethyl ether (DME) to move toward a sustainable, clean energy economy.

Both hydrogen and ammonia are very commonly used industrial products, such as for oil refining, and food and fertilizer production²⁴. Much is known about their chemical and physical properties and they are readily available. Using hydrogen and ammonia as a replacement for fossil fuel, however, is currently a niche but emerging practice. DME, on the other hand, is frequently blended in liquid petroleum gas (LPG) or diesel and can potentially be used as a substitute for both²⁵. Hydrogen is used in the process of making both ammonia and DME and can be categorized by two separate markets: merchant, where it is

²² Denali Commission Grant Close out Report, Grant No. 01117-220607.

²³ Hatch Acres Corporation, "AK-BC Intertie Feasibility Study SE Alaska," Pg. 5, 2007, prepared for the Denali Commission.

²⁴ Lipman, T., "An Overview of Hydrogen Production and Storage Systems with Renewable Hydrogen Case Studies," May 2011, Clean Energy States Alliance, <http://www.cleanenergystates.org/projects/hydrogen-and-fuel-cells/hydrogen-and-fuel-cell-resource-library/resource/an-overview-of-hydrogen-production-and-storage-systems-with-renewable-hydrogen-case-studies>, accessed 15 Oct. 2011.

²⁵ Miler, J. D., Zmierczak, W.W., "Dimethyl Ether – A New Synthetic Fuel Commodity and Chemical Building Block," 2005.

produced with the intent of distribution to other locations, and localized, where the hydrogen is produced and utilized on site²⁶. Ammonia and DME are created through more complex processes using hydrogen as a feedstock and can be considered end products for energy storage and shipping that, from some perspectives, have more desirable chemical and physical properties than pure hydrogen. There are several challenges unique to each of these alternative fuels—primarily cost—but they all show some promise in the long-term for moving captured and converted energy over long distances.

Hydrogen

The most common (and currently least costly) method of hydrogen production is by the creation of synthesis gas through steam methane reformation (SMR) of natural gas or gasification of hydrocarbon fuels. SMR of natural gas accounts for nearly 95% of hydrogen production in the United States²⁷. Alaska has an estimated 35 trillion cubic feet (CF) of natural gas located on the North Slope that is currently stranded in the absence of a pipeline or other way to export the gas²⁸. SMR of natural gas is a mature technology and operates at fairly high efficiencies, up to 80-85% in large-scale units²⁹.

A second, less common (and more costly) method of producing hydrogen is by electrolysis, where H₂O molecules are split into separate elements of hydrogen and oxygen by an electrolyzer. This process can be achieved using electricity from an integrated grid, or by onsite power generation, although with today's technology it is less efficient (ranging between 55-75%)³⁰. The cost of electricity alone typically accounts for between 17% and 58% of the cost for hydrogen production, depending on the scale of the operation³¹. However, as compared to the SMR process with fossil fuels described above, production of hydrogen via electrolysis can be powered by renewable resources such as wind, geothermal, etc. In some cases, such as large wind farms in the Lower 48 that are constrained by transmission contracts to the grid and are hence idled for significant periods of time, the marginal electricity costs can be quite small. Electrolyzers, however, do have a high capital cost and require significant amounts of hydrogen production to operate at economies of scale. This is still a weak link in the production cost of hydrogen using renewable electricity. In addition, use of hydrogen as a fuel through fuel cells is a fairly immature technology and is quite expensive, though fuel cells are not the only means of converting hydrogen into useful kinetic energy.

Hydrogen has an extremely high energy content, but its energy density is very low, thus generally requiring pressurization for large-scale shipping and/or space-efficient storage, which adds costs and complication to the overall process. Currently, the most cost effective method of transportation is via pipeline; however suitable pipeline infrastructure is expensive. Hydrogen causes embrittlement of

²⁶ Lipman, T., "An Overview of Hydrogen Production and Storage Systems with Renewable Hydrogen Case Studies," pg. 20.

²⁷ New York State Energy Research and Development Authority, "Hydrogen Fact Sheet – Hydrogen Production Steam Methane Reforming," <http://www.getenergysmart.org/files/hydrogeneducation/6hydrogenproductionsteammethanereforming.pdf>, accessed 8 Oct. 2011.

²⁸ Thomas, C. P., et al, "Alaska North Slope Oil and Gas A Promising Future or an Area in Decline?" April 2009, <http://www.netl.doe.gov/technologies/oil-gas/publications/EPreports/ANSSummaryReportFinalAugust2007.pdf>, accessed 8 Oct. 2011.

²⁹ International Energy Agency, "Energy Technology Essentials - Hydrogen Production and Distribution," April 2007, <http://www.iea.org/techno/essentials.htm>, accessed 8 Oct. 2011.

³⁰ *Ibid.*

³¹ Ivy, J., "Summary of Electrolytic Hydrogen Production," Sept. 2004.

metals, increasing the likelihood of leakage over time³². Nonetheless, development of hydrogen pipelines are increasing, both for oil refining and other chemical processes³³ and as part of the natural gas pipeline infrastructure for storing otherwise stranded wind energy³⁴. These physical constraints with storing and shipping pure hydrogen have led to searches for alternative chemical and/or physical structures that include “clean” hydrogen but have more favorable commercial properties, including higher energy density, larger molecules, less leakage and less metal embrittlement.

Ammonia

Ammonia is made through the combination of hydrogen and nitrogen, typically using the Haber-Bosch process, which is energy intensive. Produced primarily in China from coal and natural gas, ammonia is one of the most commonly used and transported industrial chemicals on the planet, though its main use is for fertilizer. In 2005, non-fertilizer use of US-produced ammonia was only 11%³⁵, but even so, use of ammonia as a fuel has been gaining interest in recent years. Although ammonia is considered non-flammable due to its high auto ignition point, it can be used as a carrier of hydrogen for delivery. Ammonia has a higher energy density than hydrogen and can be liquefied at much higher temperatures (-18.4 °F rather than below -359 °F for hydrogen) which makes for easier and lower cost handling, storage, and shipping. It is also non-corrosive to metal, meaning transportation via pipeline would likely not require as much cost or upkeep as hydrogen³⁶.

While fossil fuel feedstock and the Haber-Bosch process are the current commercial means of producing ammonia, there is increasing interest in what is known as Solid State Ammonia Synthesis (SSAS) using electricity, nitrogen from the air, and an electrolyzer to strip out hydrogen from water. This is a very early stage technology that has shown promise in the laboratory but has not yet been proven out on a commercial or industrial scale. The promise includes both the opportunity to use renewably generated electricity and potentially a significant increase in efficiency with SSAS as compared to Haber-Bosch³⁷. Alaska has a unique position in this effort as Alaska Applied Sciences, based in Juneau, is a partner on the SSAS development and a national player in the ammonia as alternative fuel movement that is growing in popularity³⁸.

Dimethyl Ether

DME is produced from methanol created as a result of SMR. This process is called methanol dehydration. Due to its high octane number, DME burns cleanly with few emissions even though it is a hydrocarbon fuel. As mentioned previously, DME can be blended with LPG or diesel and can readily be

³² International Energy Agency, “Energy Technology Essentials – Hydrogen Production and Distribution.”

³³ Kaskey, J., “Air Products Plans World’s Longest Hydrogen Pipeline on U.S. Gulf Coast,” Bloomberg Online, October 2010, <http://www.bloomberg.com/news/2010-10-13/air-products-plans-world-s-largest-hydrogen-pipeline-along-u-s-gulf-coast.html>, accessed 31 Dec. 2011.

³⁴ Quilter, J., “E.on to launch wind/hydrogen storage trial,” Windpower Monthly, November 2011, <http://www.windpowermonthly.com/news/1103801/Eon-launch-wind-hydrogen-storage-trial/>, accessed 31 Dec. 2011.

³⁵ Huang, W.-y., “Impact of Rising Natural Gas Prices on U.S. Ammonia Supply,” August 2007, <http://www.ers.usda.gov/Publications/WRS0702/>, accessed 10 Oct. 2011.

³⁶ Thomas, G., Parks, G., “Potential Roles of Ammonia in a Hydrogen Economy,” Feb. 2006.

³⁷ Leighty, W., Holbrook, J., “Transmission and Firming of GW-Scale Wind Energy via Hydrogen and Ammonia,” 2008, pp. 45-66.

³⁸ Leighty, W., “Alaska Village Survival: Affordable Energy Independence Via Renewables Firming as Hydrogen Storage in Liquid Anhydrous Ammonia,” <http://www.leightyfoundation.org/files/09-NHA-ColumbiaSC-NH3-Rev16Mar-C.pdf>, accessed 15 Oct. 2011.

used as a substitute for either. Only minor modifications are needed to run diesel engines with DME due to its low boiling point (-25° C) and viscosity. DME also has a much higher energy density than hydrogen or ammonia and can be stored under moderate pressure³⁹. Still, DME is around 30% less energy efficient than other hydrocarbon fuels⁴⁰. Current DME prices are high and demand is fairly low due to limited production and specialized use. Demand is expected to grow, however, especially in Asian markets⁴¹.

Though the feedstock for commercial DME production is currently coal or natural gas, like ammonia, DME can be produced from renewable energy resources, primarily biomass. This is often called BioDME. Also similar to ammonia, DME has industrial applications other than as a fuel, namely as an aerosol propellant, a refrigerant, and as a precursor to other industrial chemicals. Significant additional research and development remains to be done to determine if DME will become the renewable diesel substitute of choice. In addition, there are multiple synthesis methods to produce DME, each with varying costs and benefits, that will ultimately determine the desirability of DME as a diesel substitute. Global companies such as Mitsubishi, Volvo and Toyo Engineering are investing significantly in DME and BioDME.

Assessing Alaska's Opportunities

In Alaska, stranded renewable resources could potentially generate carbon free electricity to produce hydrogen through water electrolysis. Localized production of hydrogen can be used to make ammonia or methanol from stranded renewable resources such as wind, geothermal, hydroelectric or tidal power. As they are more mature technologies, wind and hydroelectric are more likely candidates for renewable hydrogen production at this time.

Because of hydrogen's low energy density, on-site use would be more economical than transporting it off-site. If produced from excess renewable energy, hydrogen could also be used to stabilize intermittent power systems in rural communities. Renewable to hydrogen technology is relatively new and still in development phase, though several projects, including geothermal-to-hydrogen in Hawaii, show significant promise⁴².

Ammonia may be a technically easier option for distribution, although it still suffers from a low energy density relative to other fuels such as diesel and gasoline. If used as a carrier, ammonia must be decomposed to extract the hydrogen, which requires a considerable amount of energy. Production costs are also significant, especially if made from hydrogen produced from electrolysis.

Ammonia was produced in Alaska until 2007 for fertilizer production using natural gas reformation. The plant, located in Nikiski on the Kenai Peninsula, shut down operations due to the inability to secure long-

³⁹ Miller, J. D., & Zmierczak, W. W., "A New Synthetic Fuel Commodity and Chemical Building Block. University of Utah, College of Mines and Earth Sciences," 2005.

⁴⁰ *Ibid.*

⁴¹ Sills, R., "DME – A New Clean Fuel for the 21st Century: Opportunities and Challenges," Jan. 2005, <http://www.syngasrefiner.com/dme/dmepres/RonSills.pdf>, accessed 25 Oct. 2011.

⁴² Rocheleau, R., Ewan, M., "Hawaii Hydrogen Power Park," Hawaii Natural Energy Institute, 2011 DOE Hydrogen and Fuel Cells Program Review, http://www.hydrogen.energy.gov/pdfs/review11/tv009_rocheleau_2011_p.pdf, May 2011.

term natural gas feedstock⁴³. Alaska could attract industries, such as fertilizer production, with the incentive of low energy costs. Liquid ammonia can also be used directly as a fuel, although greater advancement in technology is needed at this time.

DME has high potential to be used as a substitute for diesel, which is used in abundance in the state. Due to there being no carbon-carbon bond, DME is also a clean burning fuel. A project of note that is being studied in Iceland is the development of a zero emissions DME production plant using renewable energy and carbon capture from flue gas.

- Mitsubishi Heavy Industries, in collaboration with Icelandic government agencies and two other independent companies, has proposed to construct a DME production plant using renewable energy and carbon capture from the flue gas of the Elkem ferrosilicon plant (see Table 2). Hydro and/or geothermal power would be used to generate electricity for the electrolysis process to produce hydrogen. The carbon dioxide captured from the flue gas is then mixed with the hydrogen to create synthesis gas, which eventually goes through methanol synthesis to develop crude methanol. The final stage of methanol dehydration is applied and the end product, DME, is stored in fuel tanks to be shipped for sale later⁴⁴.

Production of DME could be beneficial to Alaska, however, at this time DME prices are not cost competitive with diesel or LPG. Production of DME is fairly expensive; there is currently limited production and capital costs to construct a plant are high. As fossil fuel prices rise, DME production should become more economical.

Place-Based Industry

An alternative approach to transporting produced energy to market is place-based industry, i.e., the development of stranded renewable energy resource for localized utilization. Iceland is often seen as successfully implementing this strategy, i.e., attracting industry that benefits from both the energy resource and location. Furthermore, Iceland is a useful model for Alaska to review, as there are many relevant similarities including renewable energy resources, small population, isolation, challenging logistics, and high costs. The following is a discussion of some of the opportunities relevant for Alaska taken from the Icelandic experience.

Energy Intensive Industry

Energy intensive industry (EII) is a general term for those industries that use large amounts of heat and/or other forms of energy to physically or chemically transform materials⁴⁵. These industries include, but are not limited to, the smelting of aluminum, mining, petroleum refinement, metal casting, the production of chemicals, steel, and glass, and forest products. In America, as stated by the US Department of Energy, "... [EII] supply 90% of the materials vital to our economy, produce \$1 trillion in

⁴³ Hermanek, P., "Agrium to mothball Nikiski facility," March 2008, http://peninsulaclarion.com/stories/031408/news_4013.shtml, accessed 30 Sept. 2011.

⁴⁴ NTNU, "Dimethyl ether production from carbon dioxide and hydrogen," Nov. 2010, <http://www.ipt.ntnu.no/~jsg/undervisning/naturgass/oppgaver/Oppgaver2010/10Huot-Marchand.pdf>, accessed 3 Nov. 2011.

⁴⁵ United States Department of Energy, "Industrial Technologies Program: Energy Intensive Industry," 30 Nov. 2010, <http://www1.eere.energy.gov/industry/rd/industries.html>, accessed 3 Nov. 2011.

annual shipments, directly employ over 3 million people, and indirectly provide an additional 12 million jobs at all skill levels⁴⁶”.

In the early 1900s Iceland’s per capita economic output was \$2,500, about the same as present-day Ghana. Today, barely over a hundred years later, Iceland has become one of the most affluent countries in the world. By reducing dependency on fossil fuels, Iceland transformed its economy from relying on a single, major industry, fishing, to a diversified economy supported by manufacturing and service industries⁴⁷. This transformation and growth came as Iceland changed from an import/export economy to a place-based economy, powered by renewable energy.

By exploiting their renewable resources and marketing economic drivers for renewable energy development, Iceland has succeeded in using large-scale production of hydro and geothermal power to appeal to EII. In the late 1960’s aluminum smelting became the first major customer of Iceland’s energy market⁴⁸ and continued to attract EII by promoting environmental conservation (lowering a company’s carbon footprint), business friendly policies (low corporate income tax of 20% on net income) and a skilled workforce. Iceland has numerous educational institutes and programs focused on renewable energy and sustainable systems⁴⁹.

Smelting

One of the more notable place-based industries in Iceland is aluminum smelting. Smelting is the process of reducing mineral ores and concentrates to metal. Most methods involve heating the ore and concentrates with carbon to reduce the other ore compounds and, with additional refining, producing metal in a high state of purity ready for sale⁵⁰. Smelting is an extremely energy intensive process. To produce a ton of aluminum, it takes from 14.5 MWh to over 15 MWh⁵¹. Production capacity for a smelting plant varies from 10,000 tonnes per year for small-scale plants to over 800,000 tonnes per year for large smelters⁵². At the rate of 14.5-15 MWh per tonne, the baseload capacity per every tonne is about 1.66-1.71 kW. It should be note that while still high in energy consumption, other minerals require substantially less energy to smelt. Zinc, which is abundant in Alaska, requires nearly a third less of the electrical base load than what is needed for aluminum smelting. Energy consumption for zinc production ranges from 3.3 kWh/kg in developed countries to 4.5 kWh/kg in Iran⁵³. At that rate the base load to process a tonne of zinc is between 0.377-0.514 kW.

In addition to high-energy demand, smelting operations require a large amount of infrastructure. Primary infrastructure consists of a power station to meet the high-energy demand and the plant itself. Supporting infrastructure includes access roads and shipping and dock facilities. Related to this need is

⁴⁶ *Ibid.*

⁴⁷ Gylfason, T., “When Iceland was Ghana,” 2008, <https://notendur.hi.is/gylfason/private/Ghana%20Iceland.pdf>, accessed 5 Nov. 2011.

⁴⁸ Elkem Island, <http://www.jarnblendi.is/english/>, accessed 18 Aug. 2011.

⁴⁹ Invest in Iceland Agency, www.invest.is, accessed 18 Aug. 2011.

⁵⁰ Geevor Tin Mine Museum, “Smelting,” 2009, <http://www.geevor.com/media/Smelting.pdf>, accessed on 20 Aug. 2011.

⁵¹ Burns, S., “Power Costs in the Production of Primary Aluminum,” February 2009, <http://agmetalmminer.com/2009/02/26/power-costs-in-the-production-of-primary-aluminum/>, accessed on 31 Aug. 2011.

⁵² Amin, S., Mining in Africa Today, 1988, <http://archive.unu.edu/unupress/unupbooks/uu29me/uu29me00.htm#Contents>, accessed 10 Sept. 2011.

⁵³ Kalbasi, M., et al., “Optimization of Energy and Production Process Modeling of Zinc,” 2010.

optimized location. Proximity to global shipping routes, distance to raw material, distance to market, and ease of access, including the presence of a deep water port, are all critical elements to the overall feasibility of a smelting operation.

As a highly energy intensive process, smelting has significant emissions concerns if powered by traditional fossil fuels, primarily coal. Norilsk, Russia, for example, is consistently ranked as one of the most polluted cities in the world, a direct result of on-site nickel ore smelting powered by coal⁵⁴. As such, aluminum smelting operators are seeking ways to reduce their carbon footprints. Using electricity generated by hydro or geothermal power instead of coal can help EII cut total CO2 emissions by up to 90% per ton compared with electricity supplies from coal-fired power stations⁵⁵. Table 2 provides an overview of major smelting operations utilizing renewable energy.

Location	Owner	Power Source	Capacity (Tonnes per year)	Smelter Type	Power Consumption (MW)
Fjardaál <i>Iceland</i>	Alcoa	Hydropower	346,000	Aluminum	575
Grundartangi <i>Iceland</i>	Century Aluminum	Geothermal / Hydropower	260,000	Aluminum	445 <i>Estimate</i>
Helguvik ⁵⁶ <i>Iceland</i>	Century Aluminum	Geothermal / Hydropower	250,000	Aluminum	435
Hafnarfjordur <i>Iceland</i>	Rio Tinto-Alcan	Hydropower	190,000	Aluminum	340
Bell Bay <i>Australia</i>	Comalco Aluminum Ltd.	Hydropower	142,000	Aluminum	256
Trail <i>B.C., Canada</i>	Teck Cominco	Hydropower	278,000 71,500	Zinc Lead	205
Grundartangi <i>Iceland</i>	Elkem	Hydropower	120,000	Ferro-silicon	150

Table 2: World Smelting Operations Utilizing Renewable Energy⁵⁷

In the late 1960's, the construction of Iceland's first aluminum smelting operation inaugurated an influx of EII to Iceland. Iceland's most recent aluminum smelter is Alcoa's Fjardaál facility.

- Construction of the Fjardaál smelter began in 2004, was completed in June 2007, and reached full operation in April 2008. The facility contains a smelter, cast house, rod production and deep-water port. The smelter produces 940 tonnes of aluminum a day, employs 450 people and has a

⁵⁴ BBC News, "Toxic truth of secretive Siberian city," April 2007, <http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/europe/6528853.stm>, accessed 26 Nov. 2011.

⁵⁵ Invest in Iceland, Energy Intensive Industry, <http://www.invest.is/Investment-Opportunities/Energy-intensive/>, accessed 6 Nov. 2011.

⁵⁶ As of this report, the Helguvik plant was under construction, which commenced in 2008.

⁵⁷ Sources used for Table 2: Alcoa Fjardaál, http://www.alcoa.com/locations/iceland_reydarfjordur/en/home.asp, accessed 3 Nov. 2011.

Century Aluminum. *Grundartangi, Iceland*. www.centuryaluminum.com/grundartangi.html, accessed 3 November 2011. Saving Iceland, Century

Aluminum Energy Questions, 31 Jan. 2011. Rio Tinto Alcan, "Sustainable Development Report," 2010. Turton, H., "The Aluminum Smelting

Industry: Structure, market power, subsidies and greenhouse gas emissions," Jan. 2002. Teck Cominco, "Teck 2010 Annual Report," 2010.

Verkis, Elkem Island – Grundartangi, www.verkis.com/projects/industry/nr/1443, 3 Nov. 2011.

total capacity of 346,000 tonnes of aluminum per year. A 40-year contract to provide power for the plant was negotiated between Landsvirkjun, Iceland's national electricity company and owner of the Kárahnjúkar hydroelectric project, and Alcoa⁵⁸. The Kárahnjúkar dam is the country's largest hydroelectric power plant, with an installed capacity of 690 MW. All of its produced electricity is sold to the Fjarðaál smelter.

Assessing Alaska's Opportunity

Preliminary EII metrics such as access to a large base-load renewable energy source, proximity to global shipping routes, presence of a deep water port, and supporting infrastructure requirements indicate that several sites throughout the Aleutian Islands, most notably Unalaska, could theoretically have the capacity to host EII operations, such as smelting. The Makushin site on Unalaska Island, for example, is a high temperature geothermal reservoir that may have the capability of producing a suitable quantity of electricity from a geothermal power plant (see Appendix A). Unalaska is conveniently located along the Northern Pacific Great Circle Route (see Appendix B), which currently sees some of the highest volumes of traffic in the Arctic, and possesses a deep-water port at Dutch Harbor. Other sites have estimated geothermal potential and possess deep water port access. Adak in particular possesses vast infrastructure, remaining from the Adak Naval Air Facility installation, and given a viable resource adequate to support the high-energy needs, could be a prime candidate for hosting large-scale industrial operations such as smelting.

Specific to smelting, Alaska has commercial mining operations located in the State that could theoretically ship materials to the Aleutians for processing. The Red Dog mine in particular, located in the Northwest Arctic, is the second largest zinc mine in the world and represents 79% of zinc produced in the U.S.⁵⁹. Currently, Teck Cominco, the owner of Red Dog, ships the mined ore past the Aleutian Islands to Trail, British Columbia, where it is processed in a smelter owned by Teck Cominco⁶⁰. If the proper incentives were offered, such as access to competitively priced renewable energy and a strong fiscal and tax environment, a zinc smelter could be a feasible investment for private industry, an Aleutian community, and the State of Alaska.

There are substantial caveats to these prospects, however. Preliminary metrics allow for a first cut understanding of potential, but do not allow for an in-depth assessment of feasibility. There are substantial hurdles to address. Many of these hurdles deal with the remoteness of these potential sites and typical Alaskan challenges such as harsh climates. Others, including the high capital cost of such applications and need for competitive business environment, speak more to the ability of developing a business model to move forward with these prospects. The following is an outline of some of these considerations:

⁵⁸ Eden, L, "International Collaboration Key to Successful Completion of Iceland's Karahnjúkar Project," 2007, <http://www.hydroworld.com/index/display/article-display/355246/articles/hydro-review-worldwide/volume-16/issue-1/articles/international-collaboration-key-to-successful-completion-of-icelandrsquos-kaacuterahnjuacutekar-project.html>, accessed 3 Nov. 2011.

⁵⁹ Red Dog Mine, <http://reddogalaska.com/Generic.aspx?PAGE=Red+Dog+Site%2fZinc+and+Lead&portalName=tc>, accessed 22 July 2011.

⁶⁰ DeMarban, A., "Summer Shipping Begins for Red Dog Zinc," 29 June 2011, http://www.thearcticsouder.com/article/1126summer_shipping_begins_for_red_dog_zinc, accessed 22 July 2011.

- High construction costs--Remote locations, complex logistics, high material costs and the lack of local labor can all contribute to expensive construction costs in the remote areas of Alaska. This is a substantial hurdle to overcome, especially when competing with countries like Iceland that have connective modern infrastructure throughout the country.
- High operations and maintenance costs--Similarly, operating and maintaining facilities in the remote areas of Alaska is expensive and challenging. These costs can often overshadow potential benefits of projects, particularly in long-term economic projections.
- Competitive cost of energy--Beyond the energy potential of the renewable energy resource and optimal location, the resulting cost of energy available to an EII is the ultimate driver for feasibility. Iceland's cost of renewable energy is globally competitive, and a stringent benchmark for Alaska or other potential competitive markets.
- Competitive business environment--Iceland attracts foreign investment and EII in part through a competitive business environment, such as low corporate income tax rates. Iceland, for instance, offers a low corporate income tax of 20% on net income only⁶¹. Such policies would need to be assessed and potentially implemented in Alaska, similar to the tax credits for the film industry, to provide a competitive business environment.

Other EII Opportunities

It should be noted that, while the discussion thus far has focused on smelting, there are other EII opportunities for Alaska beyond those from the Iceland experience. The general principle is an industry application that requires a high amount of energy, and whose location near a stranded renewable energy resource in Alaska is a benefit, or at the minimum, does not detract from the bottom line of the localized operation. Mining is an EII that is typically located away from population centers and requires immense amounts of energy to support daily operations. Table 3 provides a list of some operating and proposed Alaskan mines and their energy needs:

Some of the Alaskan mining resources potentially could align with the location of stranded renewables. Specific to the Aleutians, mineral deposits, mostly consisting of gold, have been found on Unalaska, according to a report by the United States Geological Survey (USGS)⁶². Other mines within close proximities to potential renewable energy projects consist of Rock Creek, located 6 miles north of Nome, Alaska, and Big Hurrah 42 miles east of Nome; the Chuitna Coal project along the Cook Inlet, which could possibly use tidal power; and Kensington and Greens Creek in Southeast Alaska near multiple hydropower projects⁶³.

Fishing is another EII that could be leveraged for renewable energy development in coastal and island communities. Unalaska/Dutch Harbor, for example, is the largest fishing port in the U.S. in terms of quantity landed and is home to 6 on-shore fish processing companies during the fishing season. All of

⁶¹ OECD Tax Database, Taxation of corporate and capital income,

http://www.oecd.org/document/60/0,2340,en_2649_34533_1942460_1_1_1_1,00.html#ccj, accessed 26 Feb. 2011.

⁶² Wilson, F. H., Alaska Resource Data File, 1996, <ftp://ascftp.wr.usgs.gov/projects/geology/ardfdata/Unalaska.pdf>, accessed 3 Nov. 2011.

⁶³ Division of Mining, Land and Water, Alaska Department of Natural Resources, "Large Mining Permitting," <http://dnr.alaska.gov/mlw/mining/largemine/>, accessed 18 Aug. 2011.

the on-shore fish processors generate their own energy through the use of fish oil and diesel⁶⁴. Unalaska has abundant geothermal resources that could potentially be developed given a mix of industrial customers, city usage, and other surplus uses, creating the needed economies of scale. In another example, the City of Akutan has investigated using geothermal energy for energy production to provide heat and power to the city in addition to Trident Seafood Inc., a major local industrial user. Potential power production at the geothermal site is estimated to be between 15 and 100 MW with a minimum of 8 MW⁶⁵, estimated to exceed energy needs of both the City of Akutan and the Trident Seafood processing plant, which is about 560,000 kWh and 36 million kWh, respectively. To overcome this barrier, the City has looked at additional applications, such as district heating and greenhouses, with positive results⁶⁶.

Mine	Electrical Consumption	Power Generation Type	Status	Major Renewable Resources Nearby
Red Dog	43 MW	Onsite diesel generation	Operating	Fair to good wind resources
Fort Knox	33.5 MW	Received from GVEA	Operating	–
Greens Creek	7.5 MW	Excess hydropower from Alaska Electric Light and Power, otherwise onsite diesel generation	Operating	Snettisham Hydroelectric Project
Pogo	10 MW	Received from GVEA	Operating	Delta Wind Farm
Kensington	6 MW	Currently uses 5 1.2 MW gensets, plans to install a sixth	Operating	Multiple hydroelectric projects in SE Alaska
Donlin Creek	≈ 125 MW	Diesel generation in conjunction with 14 2.5 MW wind turbines ⁶⁷	Proposed	Proposed wind farm, 12 miles from Kuskokwim River.
Pebble	≈ 200 MW	Natural Gas	Proposed	–

Table 3: Alaska Mines and Energy Needs⁶⁸

⁶⁴ Alaska Division of Community and Regional Affairs, Alaska Community Database: Community Information Summaries, 2010.

⁶⁵ Blodgett, L., & Gawell, K., "Geothermal Energy Weekly," 18 Oct. 2011.

⁶⁶ Information Insight, Inc., "Akutan Geothermal Development Project Geothermal Energy Demand and Stakeholder assessment," January 2010.

⁶⁷ Nova Gold is reportedly looking into constructing a natural gas pipeline from the Cook Inlet. Nova Gold Resources Inc., Donlin Gold – Project Overview, Nov. 2011

⁶⁸ Sources used for Table 3: Shaw, L., "The Energy Needs of Alaska's Metal Mining Industry," 27 Oct. 2010,

<http://www.groundtruthtrekking.org/Issues/MetalsMining/Powering-Large-Mines-In-Alaska.html>; Hanson, K., et al., Nova Gold Resources Inc. Donlin Creek Gold Project, Alaska, USA NI 43-101 Technical Report, 2009, <http://www.novagold.com/section.asp?pageid=15854>; Herz, S. and Gestring, B., "Anglo American's Pebble Mine Investor Advisory: Reputational Risks, Regulatory Challenges and Legal Uncertainties," 2009, <http://ourbristolbay.com>, accessed 17 Nov. 2011.

Data Centers

In addition to EII and as part of Iceland's marketing strategy for place-based industry, the country has promoted their low cost of energy, "green" renewable energy resources, and cool temperatures to attract companies who operate data centers. Demand for data centers, driven by greater Internet use for business and entertainment, has been exceeding supply, necessitating data center growth⁶⁹. Energy use is the key concern of data centers. Depending on size, data centers can consume tens of kW for small applications to tens of MW for large facilities⁷⁰, with around half of the energy consumed by data centers going towards cooling.

Incorporating Renewable Energy

Technology companies operating data centers are investing heavily in renewable energy sources to increase corporate sustainability and reduce costs. Google, for instance, recently purchased a 114 MW wind farm in Iowa⁷¹ and a 100.8 MW wind farm in Oklahoma⁷² to supply power to several of their large data centers. Other facilities such as Emerson's St. Louis data center⁷³ and IBM's India Software Lab in Bangalore⁷⁴ incorporate large solar arrays. The following are several of the driving factors in the demand for renewable energy sources for data centers:

- Price stability--Given the high energy demand of data centers, even minor fluctuations in energy costs can have dramatic ramifications for operational costs. Renewable energy sources such as hydroelectric and geothermal can provide stably priced base load power, decoupling energy costs from volatile global markets. Long term price contracting with providers of wind power can also shore up operational costs.
- Increased reliability--Many of the grids and transmission infrastructure supplying data centers are old, overloaded, and inefficient. Data centers can supplement grid and on-site generation with renewables such as solar power, increasing efficiency through DC technology and increasing power reliability.
- Regulations--Current and pending regulations, such as cap-and-trade regulations in the United States and the Carbon Reduction Commitment in the United Kingdom, have data center operators aggressively seeking renewable energy sources.

⁶⁹ Miller, R., "Analysis: Demand Still Outpacing Supply," June 2010, <http://www.datacenterknowledge.com/archives/2010/06/28/analysts-demand-still-outpacing-supply/>, accessed 10 Sept. 2011.

⁷⁰ Silicon Valley Leadership Group, Data Center Energy Forecast, July 2008, <https://microsite.accenture.com/svlgreport/Pages/Home.aspx>, accessed 17 Sept. 2011.

⁷¹ Hoelzle, Urs, "Reducing our carbon footprint with the direct purchase of renewable energy," Google blog, July 2010, <http://googleblog.blogspot.com/2010/07/reducing-our-carbon-footprint-with.html>, accessed 15 Sept. 2011.

⁷² Demasi, G., "Oklahoma, where the wind comes sweepin' down the plain," Google blog, April 2011, <http://googleblog.blogspot.com/2011/04/oklahoma-where-wind-comes-sweepin-down.html>, accessed 20 Nov. 2011.

⁷³ Emerson, Emerson Unveils State-of-the-Art Global Data Center in St. Louis, 20 July 2009, <http://www.emerson.com/en-US/newsroom/news-releases/emerson-corporate-news/Pages/Emerson-Global-Data-Center-St-Louis.aspx>, accessed 22 Nov. 2011.

⁷⁴ IBM, "IBM Rolls Out First Solar Array Designed For High-Voltage Data Centers and Industrial Use," 3 Nov. 2011, <http://www-03.ibm.com/press/us/en/pressrelease/35891.wss>, accessed 22 Nov. 2011.

As the only western country that produces all of its electricity from emission-free, sustainable natural resources, Iceland actively markets its extensive hydroelectric power and geothermal energy to data center operators⁷⁵.

Cold-Weather Siting

In addition to incorporating renewable energy sources, operators are targeting innovative methods to reduce energy consumed by the cooling demand. Google, for example, is in the process of launching the world’s first data center cooled by saltwater in Hamina, Finland⁷⁶. Cold-weather siting for data centers is increasingly becoming a key consideration in cutting costs. An Intel data center in Russia, for example, uses an air economizer to draw in outside air to cool its servers, while recycling waste heat into the office areas for heating. During the winter, the roughly 1,000 servers are cooled 100% by outside air⁷⁷. Beyond reduced ambient temperature, cold-weather sites also offer reduced humidity. A recent study by Intel, for example, showed that when using an air economizer to draw outside air, the need for controlling humidity and filtration of fine particles was not significant. In the event outside air was too cold, warm exhaust air could be mixed with incoming air to regulate temperature⁷⁸. Cold-weather data centers are increasingly gaining attention, as summarized by the following table:

Location	Owner	Cooling Source	Power Source	Power Needs
Reykjavik <i>Iceland</i>	DataCell	Ambient Air	Geothermal / Hydropower	–
Hafnarfjordur <i>Iceland</i>	Thor Data Center	Ambient Air	Geothermal / Hydropower	3-6 MW
Kelowna <i>B.C., Canada</i>	Rack Force	Ambient Air	Hydropower	6 MW
Helsinki <i>Finland</i>	Atos	Sea Water	–	4 MW
Hamina <i>Finland</i>	Google	Sea Water	–	–
St. Petersburg <i>Russia</i>	Linxdatacenter	Ambient Air	Gas Engines	3-12 MW
Lockport <i>New York, US</i>	Yahoo!	Ambient Air	Hydropower	15 MW

Table 4: Cold-Weather Data Centers⁷⁹

⁷⁵ Invest in Iceland, “Data Centers in Iceland,” <http://www.invest.is/Investment-Opportunities/Data-Centers-in-Iceland/>, accessed 26 Nov. 2011.

⁷⁶ Rosoff, M., “Google’s Latest Data Center Is Cooled Entirely With Ocean Water,” Business Insider, May 2011, <http://www.businessinsider.com/googles-latest-data-center-is-cooled-entirely-with-ocean-water-2011-5>, accessed 26 Nov. 2011.

⁷⁷ Campbell, S. J., “Intel Data Center Power Reduced with Russian Air,” June 2011, <http://it.tmcnet.com/channels/data-center-power/articles/190594-intel-data-center-power-reduced-with-russian-air.htm>, accessed 20 Nov. 2011.

⁷⁸ Atwood, D. and Miner, J. G., “Reducing Data Center Cost with an Air Economizer,” Aug. 2008, <http://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/data-center-efficiency/data-center-efficiency-xeon-reducing-data-center-cost-with-air-economizer-brief.html>, accessed 20 Nov. 2011.

⁷⁹ Sources used for Table 4: DataCell, About Us, 2011, http://www.datacell.com/about_datacell/; Thor Data Center, 2010, <http://www.throdc.com>; RackForce, GigaCenter Facility, 2011, http://www.rackforce.com/gigacenter_facility.html; Jones, P., “Atos uses seawater for cooling in Helsinki,” 28 Oct. 2011, <http://www.datacenterdynamics/node/32937>; Grundberg, S., & Rolander, N., “For Data Center,

Iceland’s cold-weather climate is highly suitable for data centers. The mean annual temperature in Reykjavík, for instance, is 31.1°F in January and 50.5°F in July. The following figure shows approximately the amount of hours outside air can be used for cooling per year, and highlights the suitable climate in Europe and North America for such application:

Figure 1: Estimated Hours of Cooling Using Outside Air by Region⁸⁰

Access to Suitable Data Connection

Beyond the availability of renewable energy resources and cool ambient temperatures, location in relation to major data networks is a key consideration in the development of data centers. Sweden, for example, has extensive fiber optic network infrastructure, a key driver in Facebook’s support of a new data center in Lulea. Iceland, with infrastructure in place to bridge the Atlantic Ocean consisting of four separate fiber optic cables linking Iceland to Europe and North America⁸¹, can be used as a hub for faster connections between Western Europe and eastern North America.

Assessing Alaska’s Opportunity

These three metrics (the availability of renewable energy, cool temperatures, and access to a suitable network) are useful in preliminarily assessing the opportunity for Alaskan application. Alaska possesses suitable stranded geothermal and wind resources to provide power similar to the various applications described above (see *Appendix A*). In addition, Alaska is a suitable cold-weather site, as depicted in Figure 1.

In terms of these preliminary metrics, suitable data infrastructure is the only lacking component specific to stranded, place-based application. Network infrastructure is actively being developed, however, that could connect remote areas of Alaska.

Google Goes for the Cold,” 12 Sept. 2011, <http://online.wsj.com/article/SB10001424053111904836104576560551005570810.html>;
 Linxdatacenter, Linxdatacenter St. Petersburg, 2009, http://www.linxdatacenter.com/datacenter_Linxdatacenter_St_Petersburg; Miller, R.,
 “Yahoo Gets Power for Buffalo Expansion,” 6 April 2011, <http://www.datacenterknowledge.com/archives/2011/04/06/yahoo-gets-power-for-buffalo-expansion/>; all accessed 9 Nov. 2011.

⁸⁰ The Green Grid, “Estimate of Air-side Economizer Hours For Data Centers (North America, Europe),” 2009, <http://www.thegreengrid.org/>, accessed 10 Oct. 2011.

⁸¹ Invest in Iceland, “Connected to the World,” <http://www.invest.is/Investment-Opportunities/Data-Centers-in-Iceland/Connected/>, accessed 11 Oct. 2011.

- Arctic Link, a proposed data project by the Arctic Link Company, consists of a 40 Gigabit per second subsea cable that would stretch from London to Tokyo through the Northwest Passage⁸². If completed, it would be the only fiber optic line directly connecting Europe and Asia, providing a direct low latency route (89 milliseconds), and decreasing current latency by 50%⁸³. A concurrent project, Alaska Link, would run from the North Slope to Dutch Harbor to Kodiak and back, following the west coast of the State. The project is scheduled to commence construction in 2012 and be completed by 2014.

Given these metrics, renewable energy, cool weather, and connectivity, there are theoretical opportunities to utilize Alaska's stranded renewables for data centers. Unalaska is an example of a location that is in direct route of the proposed Alaska Link project, possesses adequate geothermal energy available from the Makushin site, and has suitable ambient temperatures with the mean temperature over the last decade ranging between 32.9° F in January and 52.7° F in August⁸⁴. These metrics, however, only offer the ability to preliminarily assess feasibility. There are substantial potential barriers specific to data centers that Alaska would need to address before successfully attracting data centers, beyond the current lack of relevant data network infrastructure.

As discussed in the *Smelting* section, issues such as high cost of construction, operations, and maintenance in remote Alaskan locations, the competitive cost of energy and a competitive business climate need to be considered. In addition, the labor force required to operate and maintain a data center is highly specialized. Alaska would need to strategically invest in a work force for this type of facility. There is precedent for this, however, particularly in the health care industry, manifested in hospitals found throughout Alaska in rural hubs such as Dillingham, Bethel, Nome, and Kotzebue. Nurses, technicians, and other specialized laborers work and live in these communities providing meaningful local employment and often come from Alaskan educational institutes. Finally, the siting of data centers is particularly sensitive to safety and security concerns. The risk of volcanic eruption, earthquakes, tsunamis, winter storms and other natural disasters common in areas such as the Aleutians could be a barrier to attracting data centers. These issues can perhaps be overcome, as shown by the success of Iceland attracting these types of facilities, but the competitiveness and cost ramifications are unknown at this time.

Technology Development

Technology designed to harness and utilize renewable energy resources has been used for centuries and is always evolving to meet the changing needs of energy demand. Due to the remoteness of Alaska's renewable energy resources, traditional technology to generate and transmit power from renewable energy is being challenged. As interest in developing renewable energy in Alaska increases, finding innovative and emerging technology could encourage the advancement of stranded renewable resource projects in rural regions of the state.

⁸² Arctic Link, "Project Benefits," <http://www.arcticlink.com/benefits.html>, accessed 10 Oct. 2011.

⁸³ *Ibid.*

⁸⁴ Weather Underground, "History of Dutch Harbor, AK," www.wunderground.com/US/AK/Dutch_Harbor.html, accessed 20 Sept. 2011.

The following is a discussion of relevant energy technologies that are currently being developed, demonstrated, and deployed globally to access stranded renewables, and that are relevant to Alaska.

Enhanced Geothermal Systems

Historically, electrical generation from geothermal energy production has been limited to high temperature, naturally occurring areas of tectonic activity and hot spots. Conventional geothermal energy requires heat, fluid and rock permeability for production; however, these three characteristics are not always found together. In situations where there is no rock permeability or fluid, an occurrence known as hot dry rock, typical methods of geothermal power production will not work.

Enhanced geothermal systems (EGS) are a relatively new technology for electrical generation from geothermal resources. Using EGS it is possible to harness geothermal energy in locations that previously could not be developed. In areas of hot, dry rock lacking the qualities to allow the proper flow rate, drilling an injection well into the rock and pumping cold water at high pressure can enhance permeability. One or more production wells are then drilled to extract the hot water from the newly formed fracture system. The water is brought to the surface where it is converted to electricity using a flash steam or binary power plant. Use of EGS theoretically expands the scope of development for geothermal resources and it is estimated that hundreds of thousands of megawatts could be produced in the United States alone as a result⁸⁵.

Micro-earthquakes, earthquakes below a magnitude of 3, have been linked to the production of EGS and can be a concern. While micro-earthquakes are generally not noticeable, there have been some cases that have had damaging effects. In 2006 an EGS project caused a magnitude 3.4 earthquake in Basel, Switzerland, resulting in property damage to surrounding buildings. The project was soon abandoned. Areas that are known to be susceptible to naturally occurring earthquakes have a higher probability of induced earthquakes from EGS and should likely be avoided⁸⁶.

Capital costs for EGS are high, beginning around \$4,000 per kW and increasing significantly for isolated single projects⁸⁷. There are only two EGS projects in existence today, the Soultz project in France and Landau project in Germany. They produce 1.5 MW and 3 MW of electricity respectively^{88, 89}. In Alaska, EGS opportunities have been investigated, with one project initially being developed:

- During 2009-2010 Naknek Electric Association (NEA) drilled an exploratory well near Naknek, which is located on the upper Alaska Peninsula. The well was drilled to over 11,000 feet; however, problems with equipment and flow rates resulted in the project shutting down and

⁸⁵ Massachusetts Institute of Technology, "The Future of Geothermal Energy," Jan. 2006, http://geothermal.inel.gov/publications/future_of_geothermal_energy.pdf, accessed 20 Oct. 2011.

⁸⁶ Choi, C.Q., "Earthquake Concerns Shake Geothermal Energy Projects," Dec. 2009, <http://www.livescience.com/9777-earthquake-concerns-shake-geothermal-energy-projects.html>, accessed 15 Oct. 2011.

⁸⁷ Sanyal, S. K., et al., "Cost of Electricity from Enhanced Geothermal Systems," Jan. 2007, <http://nrec.mn/data/uploads/Nom%20setguul%20xicheel/Heat%20pump/COST%20OF%20ELECTRICITY%20FROM%20ENHANCED%20GEOTHERMAL%20SYSTEMS.pdf>, accessed 20 Oct. 2011.

⁸⁸ Rüter, H., "The Geothermal Industry in Germany – regulatory framework," Jan. 2011, <http://www.r-e-a.net/document-library/events/rea-events-2011/Professor%20Horst%20Ruter%20paper.pdf>, accessed 10 Nov. 2011.

⁸⁹ Genter, A., et al., "Current Status of the EGS Soultz Geothermal Project," April 2010, <http://b-dig.iie.org.mx/BibDig/P10-0464/pdf/3124.pdf>, accessed 10 Nov. 2011.

NEA filing for bankruptcy. NEA is planning to sell its drill rig to pay back creditors, although, they will retain the geothermal property in the event that they are able to receive more funding from DOE grant funds⁹⁰. Development of a 25 MW enhanced geothermal system (EGS) generation plant was the objective for the project⁹¹.

EGS is still an immature technology, and as such faces substantial economic and technical hurdles. In addition, identifying sites that can be efficiently developed using EGS is difficult, as there may not be any indication of geothermal resources on the surface and temperatures high enough for electrical generation could be at depths up to 10,000 feet or more. The Naknek project illustrates some of the challenges still associated with EGS technology and procedures; however, the project may allow for further investigation of the technology based on lessons learned. If the technology matures and capital costs decrease, EGS could become a relevant option.

Floating Wind Turbines

Much of Alaska's stranded wind energy resource lies in western Alaska (see Appendix A). There is vast potential in the open ocean, particularly throughout the Aleutian Islands. In general, ocean winds are usually more constant and stronger due to there being less friction over the water than on land⁹². Globally, offshore wind farms capturing ocean wind resources have been in operation since the early 2000s. To date, however, wind turbines designed for offshore applications have been limited to their location by water depth, requiring placement in shallower water close to shore. Recently, however, there have been projects advancing a new form of offshore turbine:

- In 2009 Norwegian oil and gas giant Statoil inaugurated the first floating wind turbine 6.2 miles off the southwest coast of Norway. At a cost of \$66 million, the 213 ft. high turbine generates 2.3 MW of electricity. Below the surface a spar, containing water and rocks for stability, plunges almost 328 ft. down. Currently, due to deep-water mooring needs and the spar, depth limitations of the floating turbine are between 394-2,296 ft.⁹³

An obvious barrier for development of floating wind turbines is high cost; however, Statoil hopes to bring the cost in line with fixed offshore wind turbines. Other challenges that may be more prominent with floating turbines are difficult accessibility and higher O&M costs as well as higher costs of connecting back to shore. Currently, Statoil is investigating potential locations to construct a floating wind farm. Another project has been proposed to develop a floating wind farm 9-10 miles offshore of the Oregon coast by Seattle based company Principal Power⁹⁴.

⁹⁰ Loy, W., "Geothermal Meltdown?," September 2011, <http://www.petroleumnews.com/pntruncate/158258341.shtml>, accessed 15 Oct. 2011.

⁹¹ Vukick, D., et al., "Implementation of a Demonstration EGS Project at Naknek, Alaska," 2011, <http://www4.eere.energy.gov/geothermal/projects/54>, accessed 20 July 2011.

⁹² Science Daily, "Ocean Wind Power Maps Reveal Possible Wind Energy Sources," July 2008, <http://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2008/07/080709210529.htm>, accessed 11 July 2011.

⁹³ Dillow, C., "Deep-Water Wind: World's First Floating Wind Turbine Launched," Sept. 2009, <http://www.popsci.com/scitech/article/2009-09/deep-water-wind-statoilhydro-inaugurates-worlds-first-floating-wind-turbine>, accessed 15 Oct. 2011.

⁹⁴ Patton, V., "World's First Floating Wind Farm Proposed Off Oregon Coast," Nov. 2010, <http://blogs.opb.org/fieldjournal/2010/11/08/worlds-first-floating-wind-farm-proposed-off-oregon-coast/>, accessed 15 Oct. 2011.

The location of the floating wind turbine installed by Statoil would be comparable in latitude to that of Anchorage and is farther north than the Aleutian Islands. Although no known complications due to weather have occurred to the Statoil floating turbine, it would be expected that accessibility, O&M, and possibly even more extreme weather impacts, such as ice build-up and turbulent wind gusts, would be more pronounced in Alaskan waters. Sea floor terrain is likely not an issue if the depth limitations described by the Statoil project are met.

Tidal Hydrokinetics

Tidal hydrokinetic technology converts the energy contained in ocean tides into useful forms of energy, typically electricity. Generation of electricity is conducted one of two ways: through tidal stream generation, which use the current, or tide, to spin windmill like turbines and tidal barrage, which is a dam like structure that juts out into the ocean, creating power as the water flows in and out of a bay or inlet. The dynamic tidal system is another theoretical way to produce power from tidal energy in the same manner as the tidal barrage although, instead of being placed across the flow of water in and out of the bay, the dynamic tidal system would be located offshore. The dynamic tidal system concept has yet to be implemented⁹⁵.

Tidal hydrokinetic devices face a unique set of challenges in Alaska, including debris, icing, and endangered marine wildlife, which can be injured by the spinning turbines⁹⁶. As a pre-commercial technology, the systems are relatively expensive to implement. Capital costs for Alaskan projects have been estimated to be \$2,500 per installed kWh for a large-scale in-stream tidal project at Knik Arm, and between \$6,000-\$7,900 per installed kWh for several smaller in-river projects across the state⁹⁷. As hydrokinetic technology matures, costs are expected to decrease per kWh while efficiency and reliability increase, as the wind industry has demonstrated.

Wave Technology

Wave energy conversion (WEC) devices capture and utilize energy being transported by ocean waves (see Appendix A). WEC devices can be deployed in either shoreline or offshore applications, with each application having its advantages and disadvantages. Shoreline locations have less powerful wave resources available, but do not require deep-water mooring or long transmission lines, while offshore technology has greater wave potential access and is more costly to implement.

There have been multiple WEC devices designed that fall into four categories depending on how they convert energy. Below is a description of the categories and list of devices that can be found in each.

- Attenuator: Long, floating multi-segment structures that lie parallel to the direction of wave propagation. Waves moving along the length of the structure at different heights cause the segments to flex at the joints where hydraulic pumps generate power.

⁹⁵ Tousif, S., Taslim, S., Tidal Power: An Effective Method of Generating Power, 2011.

⁹⁶ *Ibid.* Pg. 22.

⁹⁷ Johnson, J. B., Pride, D. J., "River, Tidal, and Ocean Current Hydrokinetic Energy Technologies: Status and Future Opportunities in Alaska," Nov. 2010.

- Point absorber: Float on or near the surface and are relatively immobile with a second component that is driven by wave motion. The devices use the relative motion to power electromechanical or hydraulic energy converters.
- Oscillating water column (OWC)/Oscillating surge: Based on the principal that waves push large amounts of air in front of them, OWCs work by using air pressure forced through an enclosed cavity and exiting an opening containing a turbine at the top of the device. As the wave descends air is pulled back into the cavity. Oscillating surge devices are typically used in shoreline applications. Using the waves' horizontal motion, the device converts energy from the surge of water under waves in shallow areas. These units typically are mounted on pivots attached to the seafloor.
- Overtopping: Water is stored in a reservoir above the elevation of the source temporarily and then released through a hole in the bottom housing a turbine. Water is captured in the reservoir by waves rolling over ramps on the side of the device.

Similar to hydrokinetic technologies, WEC devices are still relatively immature. Barriers to developing WEC devices can arise in the form of long development timelines, length and costs of grid connections, variable energy supply, limited economical locations and high upfront capital costs. The capital cost of investment for WECs is estimated to range between \$4,000 and \$15,000 per kW in 2006 dollars⁹⁸. In a separate report by Global Energy Network Institute capital costs were assumed to be \$2,600 per kW between 2008 and 2011 and steadily decrease to \$1,325 per kW by 2024-2027⁹⁹.

One proposed project in Yakutat has recently finished a feasibility study and is currently in the design phase. The project tentatively plans to use the oscillating surge device oyster for power generation. Capital costs for the Yakutat project are estimated to be between \$13,000 and \$9,000 for 1 to 8 devices, respectively. Cost of electricity is assumed to range from 45.1 cents to 28.4 cents per kWh¹⁰⁰.

⁹⁸ MMS, U.S. Department of the Interior, Tech White Paper on Wave Energy Potential on the U.S. Outer Continental Shelf, May 2006, <http://ocsenergy.anl.gov>, accessed 15 Oct. 2011.

⁹⁹ Meisen, P., Loiseau, A., "Ocean Energy Technologies for Renewable Energy Generation," Aug. 2009, <http://www.geni.org/globalenergy/research/#oceanenergytechnologies>, accessed 25 Oct. 2011.

¹⁰⁰ Previsic, M., "Yakutat Conceptual Design, Performance, Cost and Economic Wave Power Feasibility Study," Dec. 2009, <http://oceanenergy.epri.com/waveenergy.html#reports>, accessed 10 Oct. 2011.

Conclusions and Recommendations

During this initial investigation of stranded renewables in Alaska, it became apparent that the breadth and depth of detailed technical and economic information required to fully inform this discussion is substantial. As a first step, we have focused this report on introducing the tremendous renewable energy resources in Alaska, the success of countries like Iceland and Norway in developing their perceived similar resources, and some of the relevant methods and technologies that could have theoretical application in Alaska. The drivers and particulars are, of course, much more complicated.

Preliminary Findings

From a general level, it is clear from the experience of countries like Norway and Iceland that developing commercial- and export-scale renewable energy resources requires strong supportive policy and strategic government planning. To date, Alaska has neither outside of oil and gas policy specifically targeting state revenue generation. Such policy and planning efforts are essential for Alaska to utilize its stranded renewable resources to meet domestic energy needs and seek new opportunities for economic growth and diversification.

Fully understanding Alaska's potential for developing stranded renewable energy is limited in part due to a lack of comprehensive resource assessments. For example, there is currently limited information related to state-wide and site-specific geothermal resource potential or wave and tidal potential. This hampers strategic energy planning, business planning, and project development. As a comparison, the State currently takes an active role in wind resource assessments for feasibility and planning efforts, a vital step to developing the many recent wind projects over the past several years. The State could translate these efforts to resources such as geothermal and ocean energy, although it is true that such efforts are much more expensive than wind resource assessments. Specific to ocean energy, the State has begun such efforts by partnering with NOAA and conducting a comprehensive resource assessment of Cook Inlet.

In terms of technological development, HVDC technology has significant potential for use in Alaska, theoretically allowing for access, integration, distribution, and even export of stranded renewable energy resources. Countries like Norway are widely utilizing this form of transmission and pioneering its use for exporting renewable energy, and have had much economic success in doing so. These opportunities for Alaska, however, have had little technical and economic analysis, particularly in the context of state-wide strategic infrastructure planning. The "Alaska Backbone" concept, for instance, is an exciting proposal on paper, but has had little comparative analysis to current proposed infrastructure projects like a natural gas pipeline, let alone an independent feasibility analysis. In addition, much of the innovative HVDC technology that are critical to these opportunities for Alaska, such as multi-terminal HVDC grids and small-scale HVDC converters, are in the pre-commercial stage and have had limited demonstration and deployment.

Place-based industry, smelting and data centers in particular, theoretically have great potential in the State given Alaska's position relative to global transportation lanes, the availability of commercial-scale renewable resources, and other advantages such as cool ambient temperatures and geographic location. It is important to note, however, that the economic assessment of these opportunities has not

been investigated in detail enough to truly justify recommendation. These efforts in particular would need to be linked to a strong supportive State policy, similar to the high level of government support and incentives offered by countries like Iceland. Minor advantages in the overall cost of electricity have dramatic ramifications for the bottom line of such operations. Ultimately, the delivered cost of electricity for any large operation would need to be competitive with prices offered by other Arctic nations possessing lower barriers, real or perceived, associated with distance from major support centers.

Technology development is a critical activity to both accessing and utilizing Alaska's stranded renewable energy resources. With the enactment of the Emerging Energy Technology Fund (AS 42.45.375) in 2011, the State has recognized this role, and the need for innovation in expanding our available energy solutions. There is still need, however, to integrate this program and others into an overall strategic energy plan for the State, ensuring that promising solutions have the opportunity to be implemented in the future, and that Alaskan businesses can be competitive in emerging energy markets.

Next Steps

The goal of this paper was to introduce the topic of stranded renewables in Alaska and outline a framework by which to formally consider the topic. It is clear that there is much more research needed to further inform a serious discussion on the development potential of Alaska's stranded energy resources. As a next step, ACEP and NREL propose conducting a more comprehensive assessment that better delineates that opportunities and challenges associated with development of stranded energy resources. The following list summarized some opportunities for a more detailed analysis, as identified by this paper, and mentions potential key partner organizations in addition to the authors of this report:

- **Policy Assessment:** It is recommend completing a detailed policy review of analogous countries like Iceland, Norway, and Canada specifically focused on the development and utilization of stranded renewables and relevant lessons learned for Alaska, given the State's political framework and current economic climate. Organizations such as the Institute of Social and Economic Research (ISER), Renewable Energy Alaska Project (REAP) and the Institute of the North would be key partners in such an effort.
- **Shipping and the Arctic:** Given the current decrease in sea ice in the Arctic, better assessing the foreseen challenges and opportunities associated with accessing and developing Alaska's stranded renewable energy resources should be a priority at both the State and Federal level. Organizations such as the Institute of the North and the Arctic Counsel, and forums such as the Arctic Imperative are important organizations to engage, in coordination with a broader Arctic community.
- **Alternative Fuels:** The issues surrounding the production of alternative fuels is very complex, as it touches on many interlinking issues including strategic energy and infrastructure planning, economic development, international markets, technology implementation, and economics. It is also a key aspect to understanding the economics and opportunity of stranded renewable development. It is recommend conducting a more comprehensive investigation of the opportunities and challenges specific to alternative fuel production in comparison to other

proposed options relevant to stranded renewables. In addition to NREL, ISER, the Alaska Energy Authority, the Arctic Energy Office, other State, Federal, and University entities, and key private sector analysts and industry members would be vital to sufficiently addressing such a complex component to this topic.

- **Economic Assessment:** To this point, the challenges and opportunities of developing stranded renewables have not been addressed through the lens of a comprehensive economic assessment. This aspect is critical to furthering the discussion, whether related to policy development or specific opportunities such as HVDC transmission. Potential partners range from State and Federal economic ,regulatory, and resource entities, to regional government, economic, and development entities to private sector consulting and project firms.
- **Case Studies:** Specific and detailed case studies on relevant theoretical projects are needed to better shape and inform future discussion on this topic. Examples include a smelting operation or data center on Unalaska, or investigating the development of HVDC infrastructure for utilization of North Slope natural gas, rural transmission, or access to a discrete stranded resource. Potential partners are wide-ranging depending on the resource, project, and focus of the case study.
- **HVDC:** In order to further assess the opportunities for HVDC in Alaska, close monitoring of current activities and lessons learned internationally needs to occur. In Canada, for instance, the government of Manitoba is seeking to connect its most remote communities through innovative transmission methods. Small-scale HVDC transmission is of particular interest, and if implemented, could provide a source of critical lessons learned for Alaska. Monitoring the development of relevant HVDC infrastructure, and perhaps pursuing the demonstration of this technology here in Alaska, are also important activities. Finally, detailed economic assessments of proposed and potential HVDC solutions is critical, as little analysis has been formally completed, particularly in comparison with other currently proposed energy infrastructure solutions for the State. Key partners include AEA, ISER, the Department of Labor, the Alaska Power Association and its member utilities, and the Cooperative Research Network.

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Appendix A: Overview of Stranded Renewables in Alaska

Resources

Alaska is home to some of the Nation's most abundant and diverse renewable energy resources, including geothermal, wind, hydroelectric, ocean, biomass, river and even solar and biomass. Due to remoteness and lack of accessibility, much of Alaska's renewable energy resources are considered stranded. For the purpose of this discussion, the focus is on those stranded renewable energy resources that could theoretically supply commercial- and export-scale quantities of power, i.e. geothermal, wind, ocean (tidal and wave), and river (hydroelectric and hydrokinetic). The following is a brief overview of Alaska's stranded renewable energy resources including a discussion of type, location, and theoretical potential.

Geothermal

In 2008 the United States Geological Survey (USGS) estimated capacity of all known geothermal resources in Alaska at a mean of 677 MW over the next 30 years with a low range of 236 MW and a high of 1,359 MW¹²². Alaska's geothermal potential, however, is estimated from only a few existing wells and geophysical surveys of geothermal resources that are visible from the surface. Due to the high costs of exploration, many known and potential geothermal sites have not been extensively explored. Blind geothermal systems throughout Alaska could exist but are difficult to identify, as there are no physical characteristics on the surface¹²³. Unidentified geothermal resources for Alaska are estimated to add an average of 1,788 MW, with a low of 537 MW and a high of 4,256 MW¹²⁴.

Alaska's geothermal resources are predominantly found in four regions across the state (see Figure A1-1): the Interior, which stretches from the Canadian border to the Seward Peninsula, the Southeast region, the Wrangle Mountains, and the Southwest region, which consists of the Alaska Peninsula and Aleutian Islands¹²⁵.

Geothermal resources generally occur in geological areas that have high tectonic activity, sedimentary basins, and areas with active volcanism, such as along plate boundaries¹²⁶. Areas along plate boundaries are known as subduction zones or rift zones depending on the movement of the plates. In Alaska's case, the Aleutian Islands are located along a subduction zone, where the Pacific lithospheric plate is pushed under the North American lithospheric plate as they move toward one another¹²⁷. Through the subduction process, magma moves to the surface in a magmatic chamber.

¹²² Brookhart, T., et al., "Geothermal Energy Resources and Policies of the Western States," July 2009, http://www.blm.gov/pgdata/etc/medialib/blm/wo/MINERALS_REALTY_AND_RESOURCE_PROTECTION/_energy/geothermal_eis.Par.68458.File.dat/Geothermal_Resources_and_Policies_Western_US.pdf, accessed 18 Sept. 2011.

¹²³ Benoit, D., "Geothermal and Alaska," Nov. 2008.

¹²⁴ Brookhart, T., et al., "Geothermal Energy Resources and Policies of the Western States."

¹²⁵ Alaska Energy Authority, 2009 Renewable Energy Atlas of Alaska, May 2009, <http://www.akenergyauthority.org/publications.html>, accessed 20 July 2011.

¹²⁶ Benoit, D., "Geothermal and Alaska," Nov. 2008.

¹²⁷ Motyka, R. J., et al., "Geothermal Resources of the Aleutian Arc," 1993, <http://www.dggs.dnr.state.ak.us/pubs/id/2314>, accessed 10 Sept. 2011.

Figure A1-1: Alaska Geothermal Resources¹²⁸

Contrarily, rift zones are where two lithospheric plates move away from one another causing fracturing and faults. Magma is able to move toward the surface easily through the splitting effect caused by rifting and is distributed horizontally throughout the area, opposed to being confined to magmatic chambers, such as in subduction zones. It is important to note that Iceland, a country often used for comparison to Alaska in terms of geothermal potential, is primarily a rift zone. This geologic condition is not present in Alaska, except for perhaps some weak rifting in the Seward Peninsula¹²⁹.

The Southwest region, located on the “Ring of Fire,” has the highest known geothermal capabilities in the state. At least 14 sites have been identified that potentially have high-temperature reservoirs (>302 °F) along the Aleutian arc, with a combined estimated potential to produce greater than 1,000 MW of electricity over a 30 year electrical production period¹³⁰. Geothermal resources within this region are found in the forms of thermal springs, geysers and fumarole fields¹³¹. Exploratory wells drilled at Mt. Makushin on Unalaska Island and Hot Spring Valley on Akutan Island have shown temperatures to be greater than 302 °F at both sites.

The Wrangle Mountains region is also comprised of a series of volcanoes. Geothermal capabilities are

¹²⁸ Data courtesy of Alaska Energy Authority, Alaska Volcano Observatory, Oregon Institute of Technology, Resource Data Inc. Aleutian well information from Motyka, R.J., Moorman, M.A., and Liss, S.A., 1983, Geothermal resources of Alaska: Alaska Division of Geological & Geophysical Surveys Miscellaneous Publication 8, 1 sheet, scale 1:2,500,000.

¹²⁹ Alaska Energy Authority, Renewable Energy Alaska Project, “2009 Renewable Energy Atlas,” <http://www.akenergyauthority.org/publications.html>, accessed 20 July 2011.

¹³⁰ Motyka, R. J., et al., “Geothermal Resources of the Aleutian Arc,” 1993, <http://www.dggs.dnr.state.ak.us/pubs/id/2314>, accessed 10 Sept. 2011.

¹³¹ Alaska Energy Authority, Renewable Energy Alaska Project. “2009 Renewable Energy Atlas.”

- The Aleutian Island of Unalaska hosts one of the highest estimated geothermal resources in the state. The Makushin geothermal region has an approximate temperature of 396 °F at 2,000 feet below the surface. Construction of an 18 MW electrical generation facility has been proposed to transmit electricity to the City of Unalaska and Dutch Harbor¹³⁶.
- Mt. Spurr is located 75 miles southwest of Anchorage. Two exploration wells approximately 1,000 feet deep were drilled during the summer of 2010. The exploration showed promising results of possible high temperature geothermal resources and was estimated to produce 50-100 MW of electricity for the Railbelt¹³⁷; however, the exploration well drilled during the summer of 2011 provided discouraging results. Although the 3,988 foot test well showed temperatures to be less than needed, exploration at the site is scheduled to continue¹³⁸.
- During 2009-2010 Naknek Electric Association (NEA) drilled an exploratory well near Naknek, which is located on the upper Alaska Peninsula. The well was drilled to over 11,000 feet, but problems with equipment and flow rates resulted in the project shutting down and NEA filing for bankruptcy¹³⁹. Development of a 25 MW enhanced geothermal system (EGS) generation plant was the objective for the project¹⁴⁰.
- Pilgrim Hot Springs, located on the Seward Peninsula about 60 miles from Nome, is a low to moderate geothermal source. In 1982, six test wells were drilled at depths between 150 and 1,000 feet. Each test well produced temperatures around 194 °F. Currently, studies are being conducted for sustainability of a 5 MW electrical generation facility as well as for direct use heating¹⁴¹.

Wind

Alaska has an abundance of potential wind resources, hosting the largest area of class 7 wind power in the United States¹⁴². Topography in Alaska varies significantly across the state, causing certain regions to be more susceptible to higher wind resources. Coastal areas such as Northern and Western Alaska, islands in the Gulf of Alaska and Bering Sea, the Aleutian Islands and mountainous areas throughout the state host the highest wind resources (see Figure A1-3).

Coastal areas of the Alaska Peninsula have a high mean annual wind power between class 6 and class 7, while the peninsula as a whole has a mean of class 5. The Aleutians have a mean annual wind power of class 7 and in some areas may have winds too turbulent for wind turbines. The Bering Sea islands and exposed coastal areas show an annual wind power of class 7, which dissipates to around class 5 further inland, about 100 miles. Bruin Bay located near the lower Cook Inlet is an area of strong winds that

¹³⁶ National Renewable Energy Laboratory, "Geothermal Technologies Program Alaska," Feb. 2005, <http://www.nrel.gov/docs/fy05osti/36548.pdf>, accessed 17 June 2011.

¹³⁷ Renewable Energy Alaska Project, "Projects in Alaska," 2011, <http://alaskarenewableenergy.org/alaskas-resources/projects-in-alaska/>, accessed 17 June 2011.

¹³⁸ Bradner, T., "Ormat says it isn't giving up on Mount Spurr geothermal," 2011, <http://www.alaskajournal.com/Alaska-Journal-of-Commerce/AJOC-November-6-2011/Ormat-says-it-isnt-giving-up-on-Mount-Spurr-geothermal/>, accessed 6 Nov. 2011.

¹³⁹ Loy, W., "Geothermal Meltdown?" 25 Sept 2011, <http://www.petroleumnews.com/pntruncate/158258341.shtml>, accessed 4 Nov. 2011.

¹⁴⁰ Vukick, D., et al., "Implementation of a Demonstration EGS Project at Naknek, Alaska," 1 July 201, <http://www4.eere.energy.gov/geothermal/projects/54>, accessed 20 July 2011.

¹⁴¹ Dilly, L. M., "Preliminary Feasibility Report: Pilgrim Hot Springs Nome, Alaska," 2007, <http://www.akenergyauthority.org/geothermpublications.html>, accessed 5 Nov. 2011.

¹⁴² Elliot, D.L. et al., "Wind Energy Resource Atlas of the United States," 1986, <http://rredc.nrel.gov/wind/pubs/atlas/>, accessed 8 Nov. 2011.

Figure A1-3: Alaska Onshore and Offshore Wind Potential¹⁴³

ranges from class 6 to 7, while the coastal region along the Gulf of Alaska is shown to experience class 5 winds. Middleton Island can reach up to class 7 winds, but islands in the gulf generally consist of class 5 and higher. Mountain summits and ridges across the state are estimated to have at least class 3 or higher; however, wind speeds can vary significantly from one ridge to another. The Interior has a few, localized areas that have wind potential but mostly averages class 1 to 2 winds¹⁴⁴.

Effects of seasonality on wind power classes are seen most significantly from winter to summer months. Winter is the season of maximum wind power, averaging between class 5 and 7 in the previously mentioned regions. During the summer, average wind power drops noticeably; however, it is still typically higher than class 3. The Aleutians and well-exposed areas along the Western coast are not highly affected by seasonality and can still produce class 6 and 7 winds in the summer months¹⁴⁵.

There are 15 existing wind energy projects and 10 that are either under construction or being planned, making wind the fastest growing renewable energy resource in the state. Many of the current wind projects are located along the Western coast of Alaska and are being developed by the Alaska Village Electric Cooperative (AVEC). Commercial-scale projects developed or planned include the following:

- Fire Island is located 2 miles offshore of Anchorage in the Cook Inlet. The project, developed by CIRI, Alaska, will consist of 11 turbines generating 17.5 MW of power and could ultimately

¹⁴³ Wind power estimated at 50m above ground/water. Data courtesy of Alaska Energy Authority, AWS Truewind, National Renewable Energy Lab, Resource Data Inc.

¹⁴⁴ Elliott, D. L., et al., "Wind Energy Resource Atlas of the United States" 1986, <http://rredc.nrel.gov/wind/pubs/atlas/>, accessed 5 Nov. 2011.

¹⁴⁵ Elliott, D. L., et al., "Wind Energy Resource Atlas of the United States."

Figure A1-4: Wind Project of Alaska

contain up to 33 turbines, producing nearly 53 MW of electricity. The first phase of Fire Island is scheduled for completion by fall 2012¹⁴⁶.

- Eva Creek, near Healy off the Parks Highway, is estimated to be a 24 MW wind farm with 12 turbines. Eva Creek wind farm is planned to be connected to the Railbelt energy grid in 2014¹⁴⁷.

- Delta wind farm, approximately 90 miles southeast of Fairbanks, currently has 9 turbines consisting of seven 1.8 kW, one 100 kW and a 900 kW turbine, selling its generated power to GVEA. 16 more 1.6 MW turbines are scheduled to be constructed at the site in 2012¹⁴⁸.

- Kotzebue Energy Association plans to add two cold weather type 900 kW wind turbines to their current wind farm, during the spring of 2012 to help further displace fuel use¹⁴⁹.
- Pillar Mountain Wind Farm, commissioned in 2010 and located on Kodiak Island, produces 4.5 MW of electricity with its 3 GE wind turbines¹⁵⁰. Three more turbines are being considered for installation.

Ocean

Ocean energy is one of the least developed renewable resources in Alaska, yet has some of the greatest energy potential. For the purpose of this discussion, ocean power is divided by tidal and wave energy resource. Figure A1-5 shows the estimated energy potential for ocean power throughout Alaska.

Tidal

Alaska is estimated to possess 90% of the tidal power in the U.S.¹⁵¹. Kinetic energy of currents in river systems and tidal movements from the gravitational pull of the moon, provide the energy to generate power from tidal resources. Generation of electricity is conducted one of two ways, either through tidal stream generation, which uses the current or tide to spin windmill-like turbines, or tidal barrage, which is a dam-like structure that juts out into the ocean, creating power as the water flows in and out of the bay or inlet. The dynamic tidal system is another theoretical way to produce power from tidal energy in

¹⁴⁶ Fire Island Wind LLC, "Project Overview," 2010, <http://www.fireislandwind.com/overview.aspx>, accessed 9 Nov. 2011.

¹⁴⁷ GVEA, "Eva Creek Wind Project," 2011, <http://www.gvea.com/energy/evacreek>, accessed 10 Nov. 2011.

¹⁴⁸ Cole, D., "Delta Wind Farm owners seek state certificate," Sept. 2011, http://www.newsminer.com/pages/full_story/push?blog-entry-Delta+Wind+Farm+owners+seek+state+certificate%20&id=15580967&instance=blogs_editors_desk, accessed 10 Nov. 2011.

¹⁴⁹ EWT, "EWT will Install two Cold Weather type DW900kW turbines in Alaska," July 2011, <http://www.ewtinternational.com/>, accessed 10 Nov. 2011.

¹⁵⁰ Energy Transportation Inc., "Projects: Kodiak Island Wind Farm," 2011, http://www.energytran.com/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=12&catid=1&Itemid=29, accessed 10 Nov. 2011.

¹⁵¹ Bedard, R., "Prioritized Research, Development, Deployment and Demonstration (RDD&D) Needs: Marine and Other Hydrokinetic Renewable Energy," 2008, http://oceanenergy.epri.com/attachments/ocean/reports/Final_MHK_Prioritized_RDD_Needs_Report_123108.pdf, accessed 17 June 2011.

Figure A1-5: Tidal and Wave Potential of Alaska¹⁵²

the same manner as the tidal barrage; although, instead of being placed across the flow of water in and out of the bay, the dynamic tidal system would be located up to 30 miles offshore. The dynamic tidal system concept has yet to be implemented¹⁵³.

One of the beneficial characteristics of marine hydrokinetic energy is that it is predictable and reliable. Areas that are most attractive for hydrokinetic projects are those with steady flows and adequate water depth. 2-4 knots is the minimum current that can be used to operate a hydrokinetic device, while optimum currents range from 5-7 knots. Alaska has significant hydrokinetic potential along the coast as well as in the interior region, since most inland communities are located near waterways that could accommodate hydrokinetic projects¹⁵⁴. The Cook Inlet, for example, has the second highest tidal range in North America and is of great interest for development of its tidal energy, though this would likely not be stranded because of its proximity to Alaska's primary population centers. Numerous sites in the Southeast, Cook Inlet and Aleutian Islands appear to have electrical generation potential of 25 MW or greater. The Aleutian Islands have a much greater potential with multiple sites estimated to produce between 75 MW and 220 MW¹⁵⁵.

¹⁵² Data courtesy of Alaska Energy Authority, Brian Polagye, reVision, Inc., Resource Data, Inc..

¹⁵³ Tousif, S. M., & Taslim, S. M., "Tidal Power: An Effective Method of Generating Power," International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research.

¹⁵⁴ Johnson, J. B., & Pride, D. J., "River, Tidal, and Ocean Currents Hydrokinetic Energy Technologies Status and Future Opportunities in Alaska," 2010, Alaska Center for Energy and Power.

¹⁵⁵ Alaska Energy Authority, Renewable Energy Alaska Project, "2009 Renewable Energy Atlas," <http://www.akenergyauthority.org/publications.html>, accessed 20 July 2011.

Tidal power has not been widely used due to the high cost of development and difficulties in the permitting process, partially from the immaturity of the technology. There are no tidal projects presently producing electricity in Alaska; however, several tidal projects have gone through the permit process and are in the research and development stages¹⁵⁶:

- Ocean Renewable Power Company (ORPC) has been approved to install and test hydrokinetic power systems in the Cook Inlet near Fire Island and the Kenai Forelands. The Fire Island site is expected to produce an estimated 17 MW of electricity and, in the future, could produce power in excess of 100 MW. Currently OPRC is conducting a fish and marine mammal study to assess the impact a hydrokinetic device may have on beluga whales, which are endangered and known to frequent the Cook Inlet. Further testing to determine the prevalence of sediment, debris and ice as well as installing a 1 MW unit is scheduled for 2011-2012^{157, 158}.
- The Killisnoo Tidal Energy Project, located at Kootznahoo Inlet in Southeast Alaska, is currently in the preliminary study phase¹⁵⁹. Natural Current Energy Services, LLC will be conducting the feasibility study to install 10 25 kW Red Hawk in-stream turbines for a total of 250 kW of electrical generation¹⁶⁰.
- The Natural Currents Energy Services, LLC proposed to install 6 to 12 Red Hawk tidal in-stream energy conversion units in the Gastineau Channel. The project would have a capacity of 24 MW and an average annual generation of 613.2 MWh¹⁶¹.

Wave

Wave energy is the capture and utilization of energy being transported by ocean waves. Total wave energy potential in the U.S. is estimated to be 2,100 TWh/yr, with over 50% of that potential in Alaska¹⁶². This translates to a vast untapped energy potential. Wave potential along the southern coast of Alaska and the Aleutian Islands, for example, is estimated to be almost 200 times the State's total annual energy needs.

The concept of wave energy is relatively new and few projects exist worldwide. No wave projects exist in Alaska at this time; however, one wave energy project is currently in the development phase:

¹⁵⁶ Renewable Energy Alaska Project, "Projects in Alaska," 2011, <http://alaskarenewableenergy.org/alaskas-resources/projects-in-alaska/>, accessed 17 June 2011.

¹⁵⁷ Worthington, M., Update on OPRC-Alaska, Cook Inlet Project, March 4, 2009, http://www.alaskacoast.state.ak.us/conference/2009_ACMF_Conference/PowerPointPresentations/Monty_Worthington.ppt, accessed 24 Aug. 2011.

¹⁵⁸ Worthington, M., "Tidal energy technology and OPRC's projects in Cook Inlet" 24 Aug. 2011, <http://www.aogs.org/wp-content/uploads/2011/05/Monty-Worthington-ORPC-Cook-Inlet-projects.pdf>, accessed 24 Aug. 2011.

¹⁵⁹ Alaska Energy Authority, "Tongass National Forest Energy Program: Proposed and Unconstructed Projects," 2 March 2011, http://www.akenergyauthority.org/SEIRP/Haines_Tongass%20Nat%20Forest%20Energy%20Program.pdf, accessed 10 Sept. 2011.

¹⁶⁰ Federal Register, "Natural Currents Energy Services, LLC; Notice of Preliminary Permit Application Accepted for Filing and Soliciting Comments, Motions To Intervene, and Competing Applications," Oct. 2010, <http://www.federalregister.gov/articles/2010/10/27/2010-27127/natural-currents-energy-services-llc-notice-of-preliminary-permit-application-accepted-for-filing>, accessed 10 Sept. 2011.

¹⁶¹ Federal Energy Regulatory Commission, "Natural Currents Energy Services, LLC Gastineau Channel Tidal Project," 11 Feb. 2011, <http://www.fakr.noaa.gov/habitat/letters/2009/Feb/gastineauchannelferc.pdf>, accessed 12 Sept. 2011.

¹⁶² Bedard, R., "Prioritized Research, Development, Deployment and Demonstration (RDD&D) Needs: Marine and Other Hydrokinetic Renewable Energy," 2008, Electric Power Research Institute, http://oceanenergy.epri.com/attachments/ocean/reports/Final_MHK_Prioritized_RDD_Needs_Report_123108.pdf, accessed 12 Sept. 2011.

- The wave energy project in Yakutat has recently finished a feasibility study and is currently in the design phase. The project plans to use the oscillating surge device oyster for power generation. Each unit has a capacity of 650 kW. Capital costs for the Yakutat project are estimated to be between \$13,000 and \$9,000 for 1 to 8 devices, respectively. Cost of electricity is assumed to range from 45.1 cents to 28.4 cents per kWh¹⁶³.

River

The energy potential of Alaska’s rivers is well known. Indeed, hydroelectricity is the primary renewable energy used in the State. For the purposes of this report, river energy potential is divided into two types; hydroelectric, the energy potential gained from utilizing dams to create head, and hydrokinetic, the naturally occurring energy contained in the flowing water.

Hydroelectric

Hydroelectric power is the most abundantly developed renewable resource in the state and contributes

Figure A1-6: Hydroelectric Potential of Alaska¹⁶⁴

24% of the electricity consumed in Alaska¹⁶⁵. Technology for harnessing hydropower has been used for over a century and is well established. Most large-scale operations generate hydropower by the use of dams, which allow for large energy extraction but can have harmful effects on the environment by

¹⁶³ Previsic, M., “Yakutat Conceptual Design, Performance, Cost and Economic Wave Power Feasibility Study,” Dec. 2009, Electric Power Research Institute, <http://oceanenergy.epri.com/waveenergy.html#reports>, accessed 12 Sept. 2011.

¹⁶⁴ Data courtesy of Alaska Energy Authority, HDR Alaska Inc., Resource Data Inc.

¹⁶⁵ Alaska Energy Authority, Renewable Energy Alaska Project, “2009 Renewable Energy Atlas,” <http://www.akenergyauthority.org/publications.html>, accessed 20 July 2011.

creating large reservoirs that destroy the surrounding habitat or prevent up-stream migration of some animals. Run-of-river hydropower has less of an impact on the surrounding environment. Instead of damming the river to create a reservoir, water is diverted from the river to a forebay. The water then flows through the penstock to a powerhouse, driving a turbine. Run-of-river hydropower can generate between 0.01-30 MW¹⁶⁶.

Figure A1-7: Hydroelectric Projects of Alaska¹⁶⁷

There are over 30 completed hydroelectric projects around the state and several others that are under construction¹⁶⁸.

- The Alaska State Legislature recently passed a bill in April 2011 supporting the development of the Susitna hydroelectric project¹⁶⁹. The proposed Susitna Dam would be the largest hydroelectric project in the state, creating a reservoir two miles across and 39 miles long. If the project moves forward it will provide an estimated 600 MW of generation capacity for the Railbelt and could be in operation by 2022¹⁷⁰.
- The Connelly Lake Hydro project is currently under a preliminary permit and in the preliminary design phase. The project, located approximately 12 miles southwest of Skagway and 15 miles south of Haines, would consist of a small dam and a power plant capable of producing up to 10 MW of electricity¹⁷¹.
- Lake Chakachanna is located 80 miles east of Anchorage and has excellent potential to produce electricity via a hydro power plant. The project would require raising the water level in the lake to its historical high by creating a 600 foot long, 40 foot high rock-filled dike. Water would flow

¹⁶⁶ National Renewable Energy Laboratory, "Small Hydropower Systems," July 2001, <http://www.nrel.gov/docs/fy01osti/29065.pdf>, accessed 20 Sept. 2011.

¹⁶⁷ Data courtesy of Alaska Energy Authority, HDR Alaska Inc., Resource Data Inc.

¹⁶⁸ Renewable Energy Alaska Project, "Projects in Alaska," <http://alaskarenewableenergy.org/alaskas-resources/projects-in-alaska/>, accessed 20 Sept. 2011.

¹⁶⁹ 27th Legislature, Bill History/Action for 27th Legislature, 12 April 2011, http://www.legis.state.ak.us/basis/get_bill.asp?bill=HB%20103, accessed 24 April 2011.

¹⁷⁰ Bradner, T., "Watana hydro would require state subsidy for power to be affordable," April 2011, http://classic.alaskajournal.com/stories/041411/loc_whwr.shtml accessed 25 Sept. 2011.

¹⁷¹ Alaska Power and Telephone, "Alaska Power Company," <http://aptalaska.com/index.php?action=switchTabs&tabID=14>, accessed 11 Nov. 2011.

through a 10 mile tunnel to an underground power plant, driving four 82.5 MW turbines and then discharged into the McArthur River. One of the biggest obstacles for this project is its distance from the Railbelt energy grid. The closest point, the Beluga Power Plant, is 40 miles away¹⁷².

Hydrokinetic

In addition to hydrokinetic tidal resource, Alaska is rich in hydrokinetic in-river resource. Current work is being completed by the Alaska Energy Authority and the University of Alaska Anchorage to further these estimates for rivers across the State.

Hydrokinetic devices are emerging technologies that have the potential to convert hydrokinetic energy into electricity. The turbines generally use a vertical or horizontal axis much like wind turbines. As water moves over the turbine blades it creates lift that spins the rotor, powering a mechanical generator. As with tidal hydrokinetic application, in-river turbines generally require a minimum current of 2-4 knots, while optimal performance occurs in currents between 5-7 knots. Water depth is also an important factor when considering optimal locations to extract energy. Ideal sites are those that have steady flow throughout the year and are not sensitive to periods of low water, flooding, or turbulence¹⁷³. As an emerging energy technology, hydrokinetics has only been initially deployed through demonstration projects in Alaska. The following is a summary of previous and proposed projects:

- In 2008, a 5 kW in-stream turbine generator was installed in the Yukon River near Ruby, Alaska. The project successfully generated power and was integrated into the local grid, but experienced many challenges, in particular debris impact. The project has been decommissioned, and the equipment is being used to investigate debris mitigation solutions¹⁷⁴.
- The Alaska Power and Telephone Company (AP&T) deployed a 25 kW turbine generator at Eagle on the Yukon River during summer 2010. While successful in producing power and integrating to the grid, debris impacts prematurely ended deployment at the site, and the project has been decommissioned until solutions for debris mitigation have been developed¹⁷⁵.
- A study by EPRI indicated that Igiugig, a small community located at the mouth of the Kvichak River near Lake Iliamna, would benefit from the instillation of a hydrokinetic turbine. The river at Igiugig remains ice-free during the winter, resulting in less variability of river flow from summer to winter¹⁷⁶. Baselines studies for the project were completed by the Alaska Energy Authority in 2011. Specific hydrokinetic technology has not been decided upon; however, plans are already in place to install a turbine in 2012¹⁷⁷.

¹⁷² Bailey, A., "A fresh look at Chakachamna hydropower," Sept. 2007, <http://www.petroleumnews.com/pntruncate/839208091.shtml>, accessed 29 Oct. 2011.

¹⁷³ Johnson, J. B., & Pride, D. J., "River, Tidal, and Ocean Currents Hydrokinetic Energy Technologies Status and Future Opportunities in Alaska," 2010, Alaska Center for Energy and Power.

¹⁷⁴ Johnson, J. B., & Pride, D. J., "River, Tidal, and Ocean Currents Hydrokinetic Energy Technologies Status and Future Opportunities in Alaska," 2010, Alaska Center for Energy and Power.

¹⁷⁵ Alaska Power & Telephone, "Third Quarterly Report – Yukon River Hydrokinetic Project," 30 Sept. 2011, <https://www.denali.gov/dcpdb/index.cfm?fuseAction=IndicatorDisplay.ProjectAtAGlance&filterfieldvalue=92>, accessed 25 Oct. 2011.

¹⁷⁶ Previsic, M., "System Level Design, Performance, Costs and Economic Assessment – Alaska River In-Stream Power Plants," 31 Oct. 2008, http://oceanenergy.epri.com/attachments/rise/reports/Alaska_RISEC_Final_Feasibility_Study_Report_10-31-08.pdf, accessed 25 Oct. 2011.

¹⁷⁷ Johnson, J. B., & Pride, D. J., "River, Tidal, and Ocean Currents Hydrokinetic Energy Technologies Status and Future Opportunities in Alaska."

- ORPC, in partnership with the Alaska Hydrokinetic Energy Research Center (AHERC), are conducting baseline fish and environmental studies and data collection on river debris, ice and silt on the Tanana River at Nenana in anticipation of deploying an ORPC turbine in 2012. In addition, AHERC has a site at Nenana dedicated to hydrokinetic testing, and is finalizing baseline fish and environmental studies as well as installing anchor points and other infrastructure to support these efforts¹⁷⁸.
- A study by EPRI was conducted for a 590 kW hydrokinetic underflow turbine on the Tanana River at Whitestone. Permits have been secured for the site, and the project is actively seeking funding for construction and deployment¹⁷⁹.

Logistics and Infrastructure

Alaska covers nearly 586,000 square miles of land and is sparsely populated outside of major urban centers. Of Alaska's 710,231 people, 41% live within the Anchorage municipality, Alaska's largest community, which represents only 0.3% of Alaska's land¹⁸⁰. Over 75% of the total population live in the boroughs that make up Alaska's Railbelt, the narrow infrastructure corridor connecting Seward to Fairbanks. Alaska's concentration of population and infrastructure is relatively small and far removed from a majority of Alaska's renewable energy resources. These factors of distance and economies of scale create the "stranded" nature of these resources, and provide substantial challenges to development.

Transportation Infrastructure

Alaska's road system resides primarily within the most populated region of the state, along the Railbelt. A few highways run outside of the main network, following the Trans Alaskan Pipeline System (TAPS) from Prudhoe Bay to Valdez, connecting Anchorage to Valdez and heading to the Canadian border. Nome also has a small road network that branches out a short distance. Besides providing a transportation route between the state's two largest cities, Anchorage and Fairbanks, Alaska's road system mainly supports the shipment of goods to Prudhoe Bay for oil production. The Alaska Railroad follows a similar structure, only serving communities that fall within the Railbelt region. The railroad begins in the Kenai Peninsula and ends at Eielson Air Force Base, located 30 miles from Fairbanks. Most rural Alaskan communities are not connected to major population hubs by transportation networks. Instead, fuel and other goods must be shipped by barge or flown in by plane.

Generation and Transmission

Diesel fuel is the main source of energy for a majority of Alaska's rural communities, with over 180 remote communities shipping in fuel to run small diesel generators for electricity and heat (AK Power Association). These communities generate electricity through isolated power grids, or decentralized generation, as opposed to using centralized generation such as the Railbelt power grid.

¹⁷⁸ *Ibid.*

¹⁷⁹ Previsic, M., "System Level Design, Performance, Costs and Economic Assessment—Alaska River In-Stream Power Plants."

¹⁸⁰ United States Census Bureau, "Census Interactive Population Search," <http://2010.census.gov/2010census/popmap/ipmtext.php?fl=02>, accessed 12 Oct. 2011.

The Railbelt power grid is the largest power grid in Alaska, running from Fairbanks to Homer. Six public utilities, consisting of Golden Valley Electric Association (GVEA), Matanuska Electric Association (MEA), Anchorage Municipal Light & Power (ML&P), the City of Seward Electric System (SES), Homer Electric Association (HEA) and Chugach Electric Association (CEA) make up the Railbelt utilities and provide power to 65% of Alaska’s population¹⁸¹. While the Railbelt mostly uses natural gas and oil-fired power plants for electrical generation, three hydroelectric projects, consisting of Bradley Lake, Eklutna Lake and Cooper Lake, contribute 177 of the 1,276 MW of electricity to the power grid¹⁸².

Figure A1-8: Relevant Infrastructure and Fuel Prices of Alaska¹⁸³

Pipelines

Pipelines are important infrastructure, reducing the cost and time it takes to transport crude oil and natural gas in Alaska. The largest pipeline in the state is the Trans-Alaska Pipeline System (TAPS), spanning 800 miles and costing \$8 billion to build. TAPS transports oil from the North Slope to Valdez and has moved over 15 billion barrels of oil since completion in 1977¹⁸⁴. Adjusted for inflation, the TAPS would have cost over \$28.7 billion to construct¹⁸⁵. There are numerous other pipelines in Alaska, which are located exclusively in the North Slope and Southcentral regions. Eight pipeline systems run across

¹⁸¹ Natural Capitalism Solutions, “REEL In Alaska Roadmap,” Jan. 2010, <http://akvoice.org/policy-positions/reel-in-alaska-roadmap>, accessed 17 Nov. 2011.

¹⁸² Black and Veatch, “Alaska Railbelt Regional Integrated Resource Plan (RIRP) Study,” Feb. 2010.

¹⁸³ Data courtesy of the Alaska Division of Community and Regional Affairs, January, 2010; University of Alaska Anchorage, Institute of Social and Economic Research.

¹⁸⁴ Alyeska Pipeline Service Company, “Pipeline Facts,” 8 July 2011, <http://www.alyeska-pipe.com/pipelinefacts.html>, accessed 23 July 2011.

¹⁸⁵ United States Bureau of Labor Statistics, “Consumer Price Index,” <ftp://ftp.bls.gov/pub/special.requests/cpi/cpiat.txt>, accessed 11 Nov. 2011.

the North Slope carrying crude oil into TAPS and natural gas to various locations, including the village of Nuiqsut. The Southcentral pipelines consist of two natural gas pipelines, the Kenai Kachemak and North Fork Pipelines, and the Nikiski Alaska Pipeline. The Nikiski Alaska Pipeline carries crude oil from the Tesoro refinery to Anchorage. Multiple pipeline projects are in the application process at this time as well¹⁸⁶. One of the largest projects in the state, which is still in the pre-application phase, is the Alaska Pipeline Project. The Alaska Pipeline Project proposes to carry natural gas 1,717 miles from Prudhoe Bay to Alberta, eventually connecting to the TransCanada Pipeline. A second, instate pipeline is also being considered to ship natural gas 811 miles from Prudhoe Bay to Valdez where it would be delivered to a liquefaction facility for production of liquefied natural gas (LNG)¹⁸⁷.

Economics

A major driver for the development of renewable resources in Alaska is the price of energy. The use of fossil fuels, particularly in rural and isolated communities, is expensive. Energy costs in rural communities are significantly higher than in more populated areas of the state. Villages can have protracted supply chains, making the transportation of fuel costly. A combination of storage capability, lack of competition and limited access are also contributors to high prices. Before materials, fuel and other goods are shipped to rural communities they are typically transported to larger hubs such as Anchorage and Fairbanks, especially when coming from out of state. Shipments are then either made directly to villages via truck, barge, or plane, or shipped to regional hubs where they are transferred to planes or smaller barges custom made for Alaskan rivers. A study by the Institute of Social and Economic Research (ISER) evaluating the factors that affected fuel prices in rural Alaska showed that transportation of fuel was a major factor for high fuel costs¹⁸⁸.

Generally, high fossil fuel prices increase the attractiveness of renewable energy projects; however, it does not always make them economical. The amount of fuel displaced, or cost avoided, is a principal indicator for determining feasibility, as well as return on invested capital. High capital costs for renewable energy technology and uncertainty of creating profit on smaller projects are major barriers to development for stranded renewable resources in Alaska. Rural Alaskan communities have small populations and small-scale energy grids that are typically unable to achieve economies of scale with renewable energy.

Special operation and maintenance (O&M) costs, immature technology and the need for skilled workers also create challenges for the development of stranded renewable resources¹⁸⁹. High capital costs and special O&M for renewable energy technology generally result in greater initial costs than the instillation of fossil fuel generators. However, renewable energy typically has more stable price characteristics, as there is no variable fuel costs¹⁹⁰. Oil prices are constantly changing and not always due to demand.

¹⁸⁶ State Pipeline Coordinator's Office, "Annual Report 2010," May 2010, <http://dnr.alaska.gov/commis/pco/annualreportarchive.htm>, accessed 12 Nov. 2011.

¹⁸⁷ TransCanada & Exxon Mobil, The Alaska Pipeline Project, 24 April 2011, <http://thealaskapipelineproject.com/>, accessed 15 Nov. 2011.

¹⁸⁸ Martin, S., et al., "Fuel Costs, Migration, and Community Viability," Institute of Social and Economic Research, 12 May 2008.

¹⁸⁹ Crimp, P. M., et al., "Renewable Power in Rural Alaska: Improved Opportunities for Economic Deployment," Institute of the North, 2008.

¹⁹⁰ Bird, L. M., et al., "Renewable Energy Price-Stability Benefits in Utility Green Power Programs," Aug. 2008, <https://financere.nrel.gov/finance/content/renewable-energy-price-stability-benefits-utility-green-power-programs>, accessed 5 Oct. 2011.

Speculation can influence oil prices drastically, driving consumer costs up as it did in 2008. Due to many rural communities only being able to receive fuel deliveries during the summer months, they are highly vulnerable to fluctuating fuel prices. Fuel prices across rural Alaska have consistently risen over the past decade as well. Between 2005 and 2011 the mean price of heating fuel in remote communities rose nearly 40%^{191,192}. In contrast, the cost of renewable energy technology has shown to decrease as it matures. Wind turbines, for example, have become more efficient and reliable while capital cost has decreased¹⁹³, causing wind generated electricity to drop nearly 80% in the past 30 years¹⁹⁴.

Policy

There is no doubt Alaska plays a critical role in National energy production. Since beginning operation in 1977, TAPS has transported over 15 billion barrels of crude oil from the North Slope to Valdez¹⁹⁵. Despite a decline in TAPS production, the State still produces about 700,000 barrels a day, roughly 17% of domestic oil production¹⁹⁶, with current economic conditions and technological advances offering new opportunity for old fields. Beyond oil, Alaska is vastly rich in other fossil fuels, such as coal, natural gas, and methane hydrates. Alaska's coal reserves, for example, represent the 4th largest fossil energy resource in the world¹⁹⁷.

Historically, Alaska's energy policies have been highly centralized around oil exploration and production. To promote activities such as exploration, drilling and development, the state offers a series of tax credits. The issue of lowering tax rates was cause for intense debate during the 2011 legislative session in order to rejuvenate growth in declining oil production. Oil revenues contribute greatly to Alaska's economy and are important to the state. In the 2010 fiscal year, Alaska's state revenue was \$13.9 billion, of which \$6.2 billion was received from oil revenue¹⁹⁸, which accounts for almost 90% of the State's general fund revenues (royalties, production taxes, property taxes, and corporate income taxes)¹⁹⁹.

Policies and incentives play an important role in the support of new renewable energy development. It has been shown that policies, such as the production tax credit for renewable energy, instigate growth in the development of renewable sources. Iceland is an example of a country that has aggressively pursued renewable energy policies to promote economic growth and reduce dependency on fossil fuels. Over the past half century Iceland has been developing sustainable energy in the form of geothermal

¹⁹¹ Research and Analysis Section, "Current Community Condition: Fuel Prices Across Alaska," Dec. 2005, <http://www.dced.state.ak.us/dca/StaffDir/GetPubl.cfm>, accessed 5 Oct. 2011.

¹⁹² Division of Community and Regional Affairs, Current Community Conditions: Fuel Prices Across Alaska," Jan. 2011, <http://www.dced.state.ak.us/dca/StaffDir/GetPubl.cfm>, accessed 5 Oct. 2011.

¹⁹³ U.S. DOE, "20% wind energy by 2030: Increasing wind energy's contribution to U.S. electricity supply," July 2008, http://www.20percentwind.org/20percent_wind_energy_report_revOct08.pdf, accessed

¹⁹⁴ AWEA, "Wind web tutorial: Wind energy cost," http://archive.awea.org/fag/wwt_costs.html, accessed 17 June 2011.

¹⁹⁵ Alyeska Pipeline Service Company, "Pipeline Facts," 8 July 2011, <http://www.alyeska-pipe.com/pipelinefacts.html>, accessed 23 July 2011.

¹⁹⁶ Thomas, C. P., et al., "Alaska North Slope Oil and Gas A Promising Future or an Area in Decline?" National Energy Technology Laboratory, 2007, <http://www.netl.doe.gov/technologies/oil-gas/publications/EPreports/ANSSummaryReportFinalAugust2007.pdf>, accessed 9 Oct. 2011.

¹⁹⁷ Ragsdale, R., "Alaska-Washington Connection 2011: Alaska grapples with rural energy puzzle," 28 Aug. 2011, <http://www.petroleumnews.com/pntruncate/890051509.shtml>, accessed 8 Sept. 2011.

¹⁹⁸ Alaska Division of Revenue-Tax Division, "Revenue Sources Book Fall 2010," <http://www.tax.alaska.gov/programs/documentviewer/viewer.aspx?2136f>, accessed 14 Oct. 2011.

¹⁹⁹ Sheets, B et al. "Alaska North Slope Oil and Gas: A Promising Future or an Area in Decline?" National Energy Technology Laboratory, DOE/NETL-2009/1385 Addendum Report, 2009

and hydropower. As a result, nearly 72% of all primary power and 100% of electrical production is generated from renewable energy. Iceland has used energy policies focusing on sustainable development, diversifying industrial activity and increasing exports and foreign investments to realize their energy and economic goals²⁰⁰. Iceland is currently guiding its energy policies to develop a hydrogen based economy, where cars and fishing vessels can run off of the alternative fuel and fossil fuels will no longer need to be imported.

Norway, being a large producer of oil and the seventh largest oil exporter in the world, has an economy that is heavily reliant on petroleum²⁰¹. However, like Iceland, Norway has become a leader in renewable energy development by creating policies promoting clean energy. In 2001 the Norwegian government created Enova, a public agency tasked with managing programs and investments encouraging renewable energy development. Through Enova and their energy fund, the government has supported large-scale demonstration projects in the form of tidal power and the first floating wind turbine. Currently, over 98% of electrical production and 41.5% of primary power is produced by hydropower, although Norway is looking to diversify renewable energy production by investing in offshore wind power. In hopes to create more investment through private funding, Norway signed an agreement of understanding with Sweden to establish a green certificate market that is expected to begin in 2012. Green certificates are an alternative to public funding of renewable projects where the end users of electricity finance clean energy technology by purchasing certificates on separate markets²⁰².

Steps have been made in Alaska toward developing policies and programs to aid in the growth of renewable energy over the past several years. The State, for instance, has backed a goal of 50% of Alaska's produced electricity from renewables by 2025. In 2008 House Bill 152 was passed, establishing the renewable energy grant fund, which is intended to allocate \$50 million per year for 5 years toward clean energy projects. The fund has appropriated \$150 million to 133 projects since 2008 and is currently in the application process for FY 2012 projects²⁰³. Senate Bill 220 and House Bill 306 were both signed into effect in 2010, creating the emerging energy technology fund and establishing a state energy policy, respectively, calling for 50% of the state's electrical generation to come from renewable resources by 2025²⁰⁴. The Emerging Energy Technology Fund has been appropriated \$2.4 million for FY 2011 by the State Legislature, which was matched by the Denali Commission²⁰⁵.

²⁰⁰ Petursson, B., et al., "The Iceland Energy and Hydrogen Policy," Jan. 2005, http://www.iphe.net/docs/Meetings/France_1-05/Iceland_Statement.pdf, accessed 14 Oct. 2011.

²⁰¹ Stigset, M., "Norway Oil Output May Drop 6% in 2011, Gas Rise 2.5%, Oil Directorate Says," Jan. 2011, <http://www.bloomberg.com/news/2011-01-13/norway-oil-output-may-drop-6-in-2011-gas-rise-2-5-update1-.html>, accessed 12 Nov. 2011.

²⁰² Goldstein, H. S., "A Green Certificate Market in Norway and its Implications for the Market Participants," Spring 2010, <http://www.cepe.ethz.ch/education/termpapers/Goldstein.pdf>, accessed 5 Oct. 2011.

²⁰³ Database of State Incentives for Renewables and Efficiency, "Alaska Incentives/Policies for Renewables and Efficiency," <http://www.dsireusa.org/incentives/index.cfm?re=1&ee=1&spv=0&st=0&srp=1&state=AK>, accessed 25 June 2011.

²⁰⁴ Office of the Governor, "Governor Parnell Signs Energy Policy," June 2010, <http://gov.alaska.gov/parnell/press-room/full-press-release.html?pr=5424>, accessed 20 June 2010.

²⁰⁵ Alaska Energy Authority, "Program Fact Sheet: Emerging Energy Technology Fund," July 2011, http://www.akenergyauthority.org/FactSheets/AEA_ProgramFS_EETF.pdf, accessed 20 Sept. 2011.

Appendix B: Shipping in the Arctic

Shipping in the Arctic plays a vital supporting role in accessing and developing Alaska's stranded renewables. Understanding current shipping routes, traffic volume, and infrastructure is important to fully assess current opportunities for development, while monitoring developing trends in Arctic sea ice reduction, increased traffic volume, and the potential for winter usage of the Northwest Passage provides a foundation for strategic development.

Current Industry, Logistics, and Infrastructure

Shipping in the Arctic Ocean is mostly limited to a short summer season when sea ice has receded from the coastal regions, ranging between July and September. As shipping lanes open, the volume of vessels passing through the Arctic increases significantly. The Northern Pacific Great Circle Route, represented in Figure A2-1, passes directly through the Aleutian Islands and accounts for half of the reported traffic. A contributing factor to the high volume of traffic along the Northern Pacific Great Circle Route is that it is far enough south that sea ice does not form in the winter, making year around navigation possible.

Figure A2-1: Schematic of three major shipping routes around the Aleutian Islands, and Aleutian harbor capacity²⁰⁶

Figure A2-1 also illustrates the two other major shipping routes which operate through the Aleutian Islands during the ice-free season. These two routes are used to access the Arctic Ocean from the Pacific Ocean or vice versa. The Bering Strait is the only link between the Arctic and Pacific oceans and has an

²⁰⁶ NUKA Research Planning Group, "Aleutians Subarea, Alaska: Risk layers for candidate sites for geographic response strategies," 31 May 2004, <http://www.dec.state.ak.us/spar/perp/aippor/airiskmap.pdf>, accessed 10 Sept. 2011.

average of around 120 vessels passing through per year during the ice-free season²⁰⁷. Traffic volume, however, is expected to increase as the extent of sea ice continues to decrease.

Excluding the Northern Pacific Great Circle Route, which consisted mostly of container ships and bulk carriers, over half of the traffic traveling through the Arctic was fishing vessels. Bulk carriers had the second highest volume at about 20% of all vessels. Most of the ship traffic in the Bering Sea, off the western coast of Alaska, is bulk cargo ships serving the Red Dog mine from Kivalina in northwest Alaska, fishing vessels, and coastal community resupply²⁰⁸. Bulk carriers are used to transport zinc and lead from the Red Dog mine to their smelter plant in British Columbia, Canada, for processing. Based on past averages, more than 1 million metric tonnes of zinc concentrate will have been hauled from the mine during the 2011 shipping season²⁰⁹.

In order to efficiently accommodate large bulk carriers it is necessary for harbors to have deep-water ports. A port is considered deep-water if it is able to accommodate a fully laden Panamax ship. Deep-water ports are advantageous in the loading and unloading process by eliminating the need for lightering. Unalaska/Dutch Harbor is the largest and only natural deep-water port in the Aleutian Islands and the western-most container terminal in the State. Unalaska Island is strategically located between northern Asia and the west coast of the U.S. and is a primary reason why Dutch Harbor has become a major transshipment point for western Alaska²¹⁰. However, there are other Aleutian communities with deep-water ports or docks capable of serving large vessels as well. Figure A2-1 lists the harbor capabilities of the different Aleutian communities.

Currently, there are no deep-water ports and limited infrastructure supporting response to distressed vessels or oil spills north of the Aleutian Islands. In the event shipping traffic does increase, a response site will be necessary. Although not a deep-water port, Port Spencer, located along the southwest coast of the Seward Peninsula, has a depth of 35 feet. Port Spencer was a U.S. Coast Guard location until the summer of 2010 when it was abandoned. Infrastructure at the location includes a 7,500 ft. airstrip, 250,000 gallon storage tank for fuel and water and sewage treatment. The port is well situated at the Bering Straits choke point in the case a rescue or clean up response is required²¹¹.

A Changing Arctic: Developing Opportunities

While winter navigation through the Arctic is still very limited, trends show sea ice extent in the Northern Hemisphere has been declining over the past five decades. Global Climate Models, released by the Arctic Council at the Iceland Ministerial meeting in 2004, predict a continuous decline in sea ice

²⁰⁷ Arctic Council, "Arctic Marine Shipping Assessment 2009 Report," <http://www.pame.is/amsa>, accessed 18 Sept. 2011.

²⁰⁸ *Ibid.*

²⁰⁹ DeMarban, A., "Summer shipping begins for Red Dog zinc," *The Arctic Sounder*, 29 June 2011, http://www.thearcticsounder.com/article/1126summer_shipping_begins_for_red_dog_zinc, accessed 10 Sept. 2011.

²¹⁰ Northern Economics, Inc., "Port of Dutch Harbor Ten-Year Development Plan," April 2009, <http://unalaska-ak.us/vertical/Sites/%7B0227B6A7-A82F-4BFC-9D02-A4B2D3A8BC35%7D/uploads/%7B7FC7249A-DE99-41D0-8F3A-4A7563B8F46C%7D.PDF>, accessed 10 Sept. 2011.

²¹¹ Ganley, M., "Arctic Shipping, Port Development, and Ice Breakers panel," Arctic Imperative Summit, July 2011, <http://vimeo.com/26432325>, accessed 22 July 2011.

coverage throughout the 21st century²¹². Shipping from Red Dog mine, for instance, has had record-early starts two of the last three years due to early ice melt²¹³. If sea ice extent does continue to decrease, shipping activity in and through the Arctic could increase substantially. However, the type of shipping increase would likely be point-to-point shipments and not transit shipping. Vessels carrying cargo from eastern Asia or the western U.S. are large, 10,000 TEU or greater, typically not ice-strengthened and would have drafts too deep for passage in some areas. See Remaining Challenges section for more details.

In 2005 a study was done investigating the concept of implementing a trans-arctic container shuttle service between Adak, Alaska and Iceland. The shuttle service would provide year around transportation through the Arctic using vessels with ice breaking capabilities. The two proposed ships would be 750 TEU and 5,000 TEU. The smaller of the two vessels would be able to operate independently of icebreakers until severe winter conditions occurred, while the 5,000 TEU vessel could operate independently year around. Having vessels that can perform without assistance through the Arctic year around would likely provide lower shipping costs per TEU. Estimated transport costs from the Aleutians to Iceland via the Northern Sea Route would be between \$354/TEU and \$526/TEU for the 5,000 TEU vessel during an average winter and severe winter, respectively. Transportation costs for the smaller 750 TEU vessel would be from \$1,244/TEU and \$1,887/TEU for average and severe winters. The Arctic Shuttle Container Link report states these rates are competitive with shipping rates along the southern route from East Asia to Europe, which were about \$1,500/TEU²¹⁴. Transportation costs are given in March 2006 or earlier dollars. The report found that with advancements in shipping technology and competitive costs, trans-arctic container shuttling is within a feasible scope.

Remaining Challenges

While a rise in shipping volume through the Aleutians would most likely be beneficial to the region, there are still many challenges that could hinder development. Although the extent of old ice is expected to decrease in the future, most ships traversing Arctic waters are not ice-strengthened. Consequently, non-ice-strengthened vessels would not be able to operate through first-year ice and possibly even young ice.

In addition, there are environmental limits to increased shipping traffic volume. The Bering Strait is the sole gate to the Arctic from the Pacific Ocean and is narrow as well as shallow, measuring 85 kilometers across and 30-50 meters deep²¹⁵. An increase in shipping volume could lead to the Bering Strait becoming a choke point for traffic entering and leaving the Arctic. There are also several 10 m controlling draft areas along the Northwest Passage that limits the size of ships that are able to pass, decreasing the economy of scales achieved by larger vessels²¹⁶. Most large-scale container ships today

²¹² Arctic Council, "Arctic marine Shipping Assessment 2009 Report," <http://www.pame.is/amsa>, accessed 22 July 2011.

²¹³ DeMarban, A., "Summer Shipping begins for Red Dog Zinc," *The Arctic Sounder*, 29 June 2011, http://www.thearcticsounder.com/article/1126summer_shipping_begins_for_red_dog_zinc, accessed 22 July 2011.

²¹⁴ Arpiainen, M., Kiili, R., "Arctic Shuttle Container Link from Alaska US to Europe," March 2006, http://www.marad.dot.gov/documents/Arctic_Analysis_November_08.pdf, accessed 22 July 2011.

²¹⁵ Arctic Council, "Arctic Marine Shipping Assessment 2009 Report," <http://www.pame.is/amsa>, 18 Sept. 2011.

²¹⁶ Carmel, S., "Arctic Shipping, Port Development and Ice Breakers panel," Arctic Imperative Summit, July 2011, <http://vimeo.com/26388205>, accessed 22 July 2011.

have a draft greater than 12 m up to almost 16 m and could reach 21 m in the near future²¹⁷. Recently a 305 m container ship, considered Post-Panamax which typically have a draft of 12.5 or more, passed through the Northern Sea Route²¹⁸. This route is only navigable for large vessels when ice conditions are suitable for travel further north due to shallow straights between the Laptev and East Siberian Seas²¹⁹.

An increase in shipping volume could also negatively impact marine wildlife and the environment in the Arctic. Migration corridors for marine mammals and birds share main shipping lanes entering and exiting the Arctic. While shipping and migration of marine mammals currently have limited periods of overlap, an extended shipping season could increase contact. This provides a greater possibility of pollution and oil spills contaminating marine habitat as well as noise, ship strikes and other disturbances that can harm Arctic wildlife. Response sites are also extremely limited north of the Aleutian Islands for oil spills or other shipping accidents and incidents. A rise in pollution could also lower albedo, accelerating sea ice melt²²⁰.

The Aleutian Islands and Arctic coastal lands are in remote regions of the State and have been known to endure severe weather conditions. In order to accommodate a greater number of vessels, many of the Aleutian communities would need to improve and expand current ports, which may not be feasible due to the high cost of construction in rural Alaska.

²¹⁷ GlobalSecurity.org, "Container Ship Type," 7 July 2011, <http://www.globalsecurity.org/military/systems/ship/container-types.htm>, accessed 18 Aug. 2011.

²¹⁸ Carmel, S., "Arctic Shipping, Port Development and Ice Breakers panel."

²¹⁹ Drent, J., "Commercial Shipping on the Northern Sea Route," April 1993, http://www.cnrs-scrn.org/northern_mariner/vol03/tnm_3_2_1-17.pdf, accessed 18 Aug. 2011.

²²⁰ Arctic Council, "Arctic Marine Shipping Assessment 2009 Report."